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Explaining Algorithms: How Transparency Shapes Public Support

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Abstract

The Digital Services Act and the AI Act adopted by European institutions require algorithmic decision-making systems to meet transparency obligations through the provision of explanations of their functioning. As algorithmic decision-making systems increasingly shape individuals' economic and social lives, this paper experimentally tests whether adding a non-technical explanation to a neutral system description affects public acceptance. The study relies on a large-scale survey experiment on nationally representative adult samples in France, Germany, and Italy in which each respondent evaluates six algorithmic and AI systems spanning finance, health, public services, employment, online commerce, and digital media. We measure the economically relevant dimensions of adoption and legitimacy, including beliefs, evaluative attitudes, and willingness to delegate decisions. Explanations yield measurable, though modest, increases in willingness to delegate. A mechanism-consistent decomposition shows that these effects arise primarily through improved attitudes toward the systems, while direct effects and belief shifts play a secondary role. Overall, explanations reliably move acceptance in the intended direction, but do not eliminate persistent concerns, especially those related to privacy. The results highlight both the promise and limits of information disclosure as a regulatory tool.

Keywords: Algorithmic decision-making; Algorithmic transparency; Public acceptance; Information disclosure; Cross-country survey experiment

JEL classification: C91; D83; O33; K20

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1 Introduction

Algorithmic decision-making (ADM) systems are no longer confined to back-office automation. They increasingly act as allocation rules in both markets and public services: they screen job applicants, price insurance, extend or deny credit, target advertising, recommend investments, and rank the information economic agents see online. These systems shape efficiency and distribution by influencing who matches with which opportunities, at what price, and under what constraints. Their diffusion therefore raises an important question for economists and policymakers: when algorithms govern access to high-stakes resources, what makes these systems socially acceptable, and what types of information make people more willing to rely on them?

The European context provides a particularly relevant setting to study this question. The European Union has pursued a distinctive governance strategy that emphasizes fundamental rights, accountability, and transparency in digital markets and public administration. Recent legislation, including the Digital Services Act (Regulation (EU) 2022/2065) and the EU Artificial Intelligence Act (Regulation (EU) 2024/1689), places transparency obligations and information provision at the center of the policy response to algorithmic systems. Yet, despite the prominence of “explainability” in European policy debates, credible evidence on whether explanations actually increase public acceptance remains limited and mixed.

From the perspective of information economics, explanations can be understood as a form of disclosure. They may reduce informational asymmetries between system designers and the public, helping individuals form more accurate beliefs about how decisions are made and why outcomes occur (Adadi & Berrada, 2018; Arrieta et al., 2020). At the same time, explanations can reveal complexity, sources of potential error, or the use of sensitive signals, potentially increasing concerns about manipulation, discrimination, or loss of control. The welfare and governance value of explanation requirements is therefore an empirical question: do explanations improve the willingness to rely on algorithms, or do they simply make salient new reasons to object?

This paper provides evidence using a large-scale survey experiment in three major EU member states (France, Germany, and Italy). In June 2025, we fielded an online study on broadly representative samples of adults in each country (3,007 respondents in total). Each respondent evaluates six out of twelve ADM and AI-enabled systems spanning five domains that are central to European economic and social life: economic applications (credit scoring, online advertising, algorithmic trading, robo-advisors), health (insurance premium calculation, medical diagnosis, medical assistants/chatbots), hiring (job application screening), policing (predictive policing), and information and culture (recommendation systems, search engines, social media feeds).

The experimental treatment is deliberately designed to mirror the kind of non-technical disclosures that regulators can realistically require. All respondents first receive a neutral description of what a given system is used for. Respondents in the treatment condition additionally receive a short, standardized explanation of how the system works; respondents in the baseline do not. Throughout, we use “explanation” to mean a brief, non-technical description of the system’s functioning (inputs, basic logic, and intended purpose), rather

than technical model interpretability or individualized post-hoc rationales. In this sense, the intervention is intentionally light-touch: it adjusts information and framing while remaining easy to ignore and leaving the choice set unchanged, consistent with the behavioral-economics tradition on “nudges” and choice architecture (Thaler & Sunstein, 2008; Beshears & et al., 2020). It also parallels a large applied-micro literature on light-touch informational interventions (e.g., brief letters or reminders), whose effectiveness often depends on whether recipients engage with the information (Hyman, 2020; Cohodes, 2022). Finally, the emphasis on a minimal, modular disclosure is motivated by the scaling challenge highlighted by List’s “voltage effect”: interventions that work in contained settings can lose potency when scaled or transported across contexts (List, 2022, 2023). By fielding the same explanation module across twelve real-world ADM applications and three EU member states, we provide a first stress test of whether scalable explanations shift beliefs, attitudes, and willingness to delegate.

We then measure outcomes that map naturally to economic questions about adoption. We elicit (i) beliefs that proxy perceived information and experience (knowledge, familiarity, exposure, and self-reported use), (ii) evaluative attitudes along dimensions that feature prominently in both policy debates and the explainable AI literature (transparency, fairness, accountability, privacy, trust, and usefulness) (Castelvecchi, 2016; Cai, Jongejan, & Holbrook, 2019; Shin, 2021; Weitz, Schiller, Schlagowski, Huber, & André, 2021), and (iii) willingness to delegate decisions to the system, distinguishing weak delegation (using the system as assistance) from strong delegation (ceding decision rights). By combining between-subject randomization with within-respondent evaluation of multiple systems, we can estimate average effects and map heterogeneity across domains while holding constant individual traits.

Three findings stand out. First, explanations reliably increase perceived understanding. Pooling across systems, treated respondents report higher knowledge, familiarity, exposure, and use by roughly 0.15 to 0.25 points on 7-point scales. Second, explanations generate more modest but systematic improvements in evaluative attitudes, concentrated in perceived fairness, trust, usefulness, and (to a lesser extent) accountability; transparency concerns remain essentially unchanged, and privacy responses are mixed across items. Third, explanations modestly increase willingness to delegate, with effects larger for weak than strong delegation (about 0.09 and 0.06 standard deviations, respectively, in our index-based specifications). These average effects mask substantial domain-level heterogeneity: for some applications, explanations move delegation materially (e.g., weak delegation rises by about 0.27 standard deviations for predictive policing and about 0.20 standard deviations for medical diagnosis), while for others, effects are small and often indistinguishable from zero.

In addition to providing these tractable statistical estimates, we use a mechanism-consistent decomposition to clarify how explanations shift delegation. The decomposition is consistent with a sequential structure in which explanations change perceived understanding, which covaries with attitudes, which in turn predict delegation (Baron & Kenny, 1986; Bauer, Preacher, & Gil, 2006; Imai, Keele, & Tingley, 2010). The direct effect of explanations on delegation is negligible; we find that the total effect is primarily mediated by

evaluative attitudes, while beliefs play a secondary role.

Our contributions are threefold. First, we provide a comprehensive causal assessment of how brief, policy-relevant explanations affect public acceptance of ADM, spanning a broad set of real-world applications rather than a single domain. Second, by studying three large EU member states under a shared and evolving European regulatory framework, we deliver evidence directly relevant to European debates on transparency mandates and citizen trust in automated decision-making. Third, by jointly measuring beliefs, multidimensional attitudes, and delegation preferences, and by decomposing the total effect into interpretable pathways, we help discipline discussions of explainability with quantitative magnitudes and mechanism-consistent evidence.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 situates our contribution in the literatures on explainable AI and public acceptance of ADM. Section 3 describes the survey experiment and measurement strategy. Section 4 reports the main results and the decomposition and presents additional analyses and robustness checks. Section 5 concludes with implications for the design and regulation of interpretable algorithmic systems in Europe.

2 Related Literature

The increasing complexity and “black-box” nature of many machine learning systems has raised concerns about interpretability for both end-users and developers (Castelvecchi, 2016). These concerns have fueled demands for transparency from stakeholders (Preece et al., 2018), regulators, and citizens more broadly, motivating the emergence of Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) as a field aiming to make AI outputs more understandable to humans (Adadi & Berrada, 2018). Beyond transparency (Cheng et al., 2019), XAI seeks to clarify the rationale behind predictions for users and stakeholders (Cai et al., 2019) and, ultimately, to cultivate trust in AI-driven systems (Shin, 2021; Weitz et al., 2021). A human-centered perspective further emphasizes that explanations should be most informative precisely when outputs appear unintuitive or erroneous (Riedl, 2019).

In parallel, a growing interdisciplinary literature documents that public acceptance of ADM hinges not only on perceived performance, but also on ethical and procedural concerns, notably transparency, fairness, accountability, privacy, and trust. In a large-scale survey of Dutch citizens, Aysolmaz, Müller, and Meacham (2023) propose and test a model in which transparency concerns shape perceptions of fairness, accountability, and privacy, which in turn predict trust, perceived usefulness, and ultimately intention to adopt ADM systems; they also show that perceptions vary systematically across application scenarios. Building on this line of work, our study adopts a comparable multi-dimensional measurement framework while moving from correlational acceptance models to causal evidence on the role of explanations.

2.1 Explanations, transparency, and trust

A common policy and design response to ADM opacity is to mandate or encourage explanations. However, the theoretical effect of explanations on acceptance is ambiguous: explanations may increase perceived understanding and procedural legitimacy, but can also highlight uncertainty, value-laden choices, or trade-offs that reduce confidence. Following Weitz et al. (2021), it is useful to distinguish (i) an “explainability” strand that develops conceptual and technical frameworks for producing explanations, from (ii) an “explanations” strand that evaluates the consequences of providing explanations to users across domains.

On the explainability side, contributions propose end-to-end frameworks that separate explanation generation, communication, and reception (Anjomshoae et al., 2019), and distinguish between inherently interpretable models and post-hoc explanation tools for complex models (Arrieta et al., 2020; Beaudouin et al., 2020). A central methodological distinction concerns *local* versus *global* explanations (Speith, 2022). Local methods rationalize a single prediction—for example, LIME builds a simple surrogate model around the neighborhood of an instance to approximate the decision boundary (Ribeiro, Singh, & Guestrin, 2016). Global methods instead summarize the model’s overall behavior, often via feature-importance measures aggregated across instances (Speith, 2022). Perturbation-based Shapley methods such as SHAP (Lundberg & Lee, 2017; Cohen, Dror, & Ruppin, 2005) and SAGE (Covert, Lundberg, & Lee, 2021) quantify feature relevance by systematically modifying inputs and tracking prediction changes. In practice, many deployed explanations (including in recommender systems) rely on feature-attribution narratives of the form “the system recommended/assigned Y mainly because of A and B ” (Nunes & Jannach, 2017).

On the explanations side, empirical research in HCI and related fields documents mixed behavioral effects, with outcomes depending on explanation format, task stakes, and user expectations. Early experimental evidence in recommender systems shows that increasing transparency can raise trust and acceptance in some settings (Cramer et al., 2008), and that explanation styles can meaningfully affect how users evaluate recommendations (Herlocker, Konstan, & Riedl, 2000). In social media and advertising contexts, explanations can improve perceived understanding and help users recognize algorithmic bias (Rader et al., 2018), while also inducing “algorithmic disillusionment”—a shift in beliefs about how well an algorithm performs (Eslami, Krishna Kumaran, Sandvig, & Karahalios, 2018). Across studies, explanations often increase objective and self-reported understanding, but do not necessarily translate into higher confidence or trust (Shin, 2021). These findings motivate treating explanations as a potentially modest but policy-relevant intervention whose downstream effects operate through beliefs and attitudes, and whose net impact may vary across domains.

2.2 Familiarity, experience, and belief formation

A recurring empirical regularity is that familiarity—knowledge, exposure, and experience—correlates with trust and adoption intentions. Importantly, familiarity may matter both as a cognitive channel (understanding what the system does) and as a preference channel (a taste for the familiar under uncertainty). A

complementary lens comes from the information systems and management-science literature on technology adoption. In the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) and its extensions, adoption is driven by beliefs about a system’s perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use, which shape attitudes and behavioral intentions; in settings involving uncertainty and information asymmetries, trust is often modeled as a key antecedent of acceptance (Davis, 1989; Venkatesh, Morris, Davis, & Davis, 2003; Gefen, Karahanna, & Straub, 2003). Interpreted through an economic lens, these constructs map naturally to perceived payoffs (usefulness) and perceived frictions or cognitive costs (ease of use), while trust affects the subjective distribution of outcomes and thus the willingness to rely on the system.

In economics, a classic example is “familiarity bias” in portfolio choice: investors disproportionately hold familiar assets (e.g., domestic and local equities) (Huberman, 2001). This broader mechanism provides a useful lens for algorithm adoption: unfamiliar systems may face an additional psychological hurdle beyond objective performance. Moreover, the explanation literature suggests that the efficacy of explanations depends on engagement and users’ propensity to process information (e.g., need for cognition), implying heterogeneity in how explanatory content translates into updated beliefs (Martijn, Conati, & Verbert, 2022).

Our design explicitly measures belief components such as self-reported knowledge and familiarity, perceived exposure, and self-reported use, and then connects these beliefs to evaluative attitudes and willingness to delegate. This structure allows us to assess whether brief explanations primarily shift perceived understanding (a familiarity-related belief) and whether any resulting changes in delegation plausibly operate through attitudinal channels, while remaining sensitive to heterogeneity by baseline familiarity.

2.3 Delegation to algorithms and algorithm aversion in economic settings

A closely related strand studies when individuals *delegate* decisions to algorithms rather than merely expressing favorable attitudes. Work on “algorithm aversion” shows that people may avoid algorithms after observing errors, even when algorithms outperform humans, though aversion can be attenuated when users retain some discretion or control (Dietvorst, Simmons, & Massey, 2015, 2018). In economics and related fields, delegation and reliance are also studied in organizational and market environments where incentives, monitoring, and trust matter. Cross-country evidence links higher social trust to greater delegation within firms or to advisors (Gur & Bjørnskov, 2017; Gennaioli, Shleifer, & Vishny, 2015), and household-finance evidence highlights how delegation choices depend on perceived competence and context (Holzmeister, Holmén, Kirchler, Stefan, & Wengström, 2023). Field evidence further suggests that worker compliance with algorithmic recommendations can be shaped by how algorithmic rules are implemented and perceived on the ground (Kawaguchi, 2021). Together, these contributions underscore that acceptance is not only attitudinal: it manifests as a willingness to rely on algorithmic outputs in consequential choices.

3 Methodology

3.1 Survey Design and Items

We study attitudes toward a broad set of algorithmic decision-making (ADM) systems that individuals may encounter over the course of their lives. The set spans both (i) systems that households use directly in everyday settings (e.g., search engines, recommendation systems, social media feeds) and (ii) systems typically operated by organizations or experts that nonetheless shape household outcomes (e.g., credit scoring, insurance pricing, algorithmic trading, predictive policing). In the latter category, individuals are often affected indirectly through institutional decisions or platform-mediated services rather than through direct use.

Our main research question is whether providing brief, non-technical explanations of how ADM systems work affects respondents’ system-specific beliefs and evaluative attitudes, and whether such changes translate into greater willingness to delegate decisions to algorithms. Because each respondent evaluates multiple systems drawn from different domains, we can examine within-respondent variation across systems while controlling for respondent-level socio-demographic characteristics.

Procedure and measures. Each respondent evaluates multiple algorithmic systems. For each system, respondents in the control condition receive the system name and a short definition describing its purpose. Respondents in the explanation condition receive the same definition plus a short procedural explanation of the system’s inner workings. After this information exposure, we measure four belief-related outcomes: self-reported knowledge (K1), self-reported familiarity (K2), perceived exposure (EXP1), and self-reported use (U1). These items capture respondents’ perceived understanding and engagement with the system immediately following the definition or the explanations (Table 8).

Respondents’ evaluative attitudes are measured next using a battery adapted from prior work (Aysolmaz et al., 2023). The attitude items cover six dimensions: transparency, fairness, accountability, privacy, trust, and perceived usefulness (Table 8). We also measure willingness to delegate decisions to algorithms using two items that distinguish between weak delegation (using the system as an assistive tool) and strong delegation (ceding decision rights to the system).

Experimental manipulation. The experiment uses a single between-subject manipulation at the respondent level. Respondents are randomly assigned to either a control condition (definition only) or an explanation condition (definition plus a brief description of how the system operates). Randomization is independent across respondents and balanced by design.

3.2 ADM and AI systems

We study 12 algorithmic decision-making (ADM) and AI-enabled systems spanning five domains: economic applications, health, hiring, policing/justice, and information and culture. This design builds on prior survey-

Table 1: ADM and AI systems studied in the survey

Domain	System
Economic	Credit scoring
	Online advertising
	Algorithmic trading
	Robo-advisors
Health	Insurance premium calculation
	Healthcare diagnosis (experts)
	Medical assistants/chatbots
Hiring	Job application screening
Policing/Justice	Predictive policing
Information & Culture	Recommendation systems
	Search engines
	Social media feeds

based work that measures perceptions of ADM systems in scenario form (e.g., Aysolmaz et al. (2023)) and extends it by covering a wider set of systems that individuals may encounter directly (as users or decision targets) or indirectly (through institutional or market-level decisions).¹

Table 1 summarizes the systems and the short descriptions shown to respondents. The selected systems vary in (i) how directly individuals interact with them (e.g., search engines vs. algorithmic trading) and (ii) how consequential the decisions are perceived to be (e.g., medical diagnosis vs. content recommendation). This breadth helps us examine whether the effect of explanations on beliefs, attitudes, and willingness to delegate is stable across contexts or concentrated in particular domains.

3.3 Sample and Data collection

Data were collected online using Dynata’s survey panel.² We recruited respondents in three countries—France, Germany, and Italy—with country-specific quotas to obtain samples that are broadly representative of the adult population in terms of gender, age, and geographic location. The final sample includes 3,007 respon-

¹Aysolmaz et al. (2023) study five scenarios: social media recommendation, human resources recruitment, insurance premium identification, medical treatment selection, and tax declaration preparation.

²Dynata applies standard panel quality-assurance procedures designed to mitigate inattentive responding and improve data reliability.

dents in total: 1,000 in France, 1,003 in Germany, and 1,004 in Italy. Table 11 reports descriptive statistics by country.

Fieldwork was conducted between June 23, 2025, and June 30, 2025. Respondents provided informed consent before participating. The study protocol was preregistered on AsPredicted (Registration #226,393) and received ethical approval from the PSE Institutional Review Board (IRB #2025-026).

4 Results

4.1 Descriptive Statistics

This section reports descriptive statistics for the main outcomes. We first characterize respondents’ beliefs about a set of algorithmic systems: self-reported knowledge and familiarity, perceived exposure, and self-reported use. We then summarize attitudes toward these systems across six dimensions: transparency, fairness, accountability, privacy, trust, and perceived usefulness. Finally, we document respondents’ willingness to delegate decisions to algorithms, distinguishing between weak and strong forms of delegation. All outcomes are measured on 7-point Likert scales; we report group means and standard deviations. We compare responses between a baseline condition in which respondents receive only a short definition of the system, and a treatment condition that provides the same definition plus a brief explanation of how the system operates. Because each respondent evaluates multiple systems, the Welch and Wilcoxon tests in this section treat repeated observations as independent and should be read as descriptive. Our main treatment-effect estimates below rely on mixed-effects specifications and a respondent-level (cluster) bootstrap that respects the repeated-measures structure.

We present results in three layers. We begin with descriptive differences between treatment and control for beliefs, attitudes, and delegation, pooled across systems and summarized by system in the Appendix. We then report our main mixed-effects estimates and the mechanism-consistent decomposition that links beliefs, attitudes, and delegation. Finally, we report a set of pre-specified and exploratory heterogeneity analyses that probe when explanations matter more (by baseline system familiarity, political self-placement, and attention to the explanatory content).

4.1.1 Beliefs

Appendix Tables 12 and 13 report mean belief scores by system (with standard deviations) for the baseline and treatment conditions, respectively, and Appendix Figures 8–11 visualize the corresponding distributions by condition. Focusing on the baseline condition (Table 12), beliefs vary substantially across application domains. Systems embedded in daily digital life—most notably *Search Engines* and *Social Media*—exhibit the highest baseline levels of familiarity, exposure, and use (e.g., *Search Engines*: Familiarity = 4.46, Exposure = 4.48, Use = 4.31). By contrast, more specialized or institutionally distant systems such as *Predictive Policing* are consistently rated lowest (Knowledge = 3.43, Familiarity = 3.07, Exposure = 2.36, Use = 2.16).

Table 2: Treated vs Baseline: Welch two-sample t -tests and Wilcoxon rank-sum tests

Variable	Mean (Treated)	Mean (Baseline)	t	df	95% CI (diff)	Sig. (Welch / Wilc.)
Know.	4.260	4.002	9.782	18005	[0.206; 0.310]	*** / ***
Fam.	3.935	3.649	10.771	18015	[0.234; 0.338]	*** / ***
Exp.	3.520	3.093	13.721	17985	[0.366; 0.488]	*** / ***
Use	3.278	2.812	15.101	17953	[0.405; 0.526]	*** / ***
Beliefs (Sum)	14.992	13.556	14.619	18031	[1.244; 1.629]	*** / ***
Beliefs (PCA)	0.103	-0.103	13.931	18040	[0.177; 0.235]	*** / ***

Notes: Significance levels: * $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$. “Welch” refers to two-sample t -tests with unequal variances; “Wilc.” refers to Wilcoxon rank-sum tests.

Pooling all system evaluations, the treated group reports systematically higher beliefs than the baseline group (Table 2). Relative to the baseline, mean self-reported knowledge increases by 0.26 points (4.260 vs 4.002), familiarity by 0.29 (3.935 vs 3.649), perceived exposure by 0.43 (3.520 vs 3.093), and self-reported use by 0.47 (3.278 vs 2.812). The composite beliefs measures exhibit similarly pronounced shifts (Beliefs Sum: 14.992 vs 13.556; Beliefs PCA: 0.103 vs -0.103). These differences are statistically significant under both Welch two-sample t -tests and Wilcoxon rank-sum tests (all $p < 0.01$). Substantively, the estimated effects are precise but moderate in magnitude on a 1–7 scale—typically on the order of 0.25 to 0.50 points for the individual belief components.

Treatment effects also vary across systems. Averaging treatment–control differences across the four belief measures (knowledge, familiarity, exposure, and use), the largest gains are observed for *Online Advertising* and *Recommendation* systems, whereas changes are close to zero for already familiar systems such as *Social Media*. For a subset of systems, estimated effects are negative for specific belief components, consistent with respondents revising downward their perceived exposure or self-reported use once they receive a more detailed explanation of how the system operates.

4.1.2 Attitudes

Attitudinal measures toward algorithmic systems are, on average, mildly favorable in both experimental groups. Aggregating across systems (Appendix Tables 14–15), respondents in the baseline condition rate fairness and accountability slightly above the neutral midpoint of the 1–7 scale (PF1 = 4.21, PF2 = 4.18; PA1 = 4.08, PA2 = 3.89). Trust and usefulness are similarly above the midpoint (Tr1 = 4.12, Tr2 = 4.33; PU1 = 4.01, PU2 = 4.05). By contrast, perceived concerns are consistently below the midpoint (TC1 = 3.43, TC2 = 3.29), while privacy concerns are mixed—one item falls below the midpoint, whereas the other lies around it (PC1 = 3.35, PC2 = 4.05). The treated condition exhibits a closely related profile (Appendix Tables 16–17), with slightly higher average ratings on fairness, trust, and usefulness (e.g., PF1 = 4.34; Tr2 = 4.49; PU1 = 4.16), while transparency remains the lowest-rated dimension (TC1 = 3.45, TC2 = 3.25).

Table 3: Treated vs Baseline: Welch two-sample t -tests and Wilcoxon rank-sum tests

Variable	Mean (Treated)	Mean (Baseline)	t	df	95% CI (diff)	Sig. (Welch / Wilc.)
TC1	3.424	3.426	-0.098	18029	[-0.044; 0.040]	/
TC2	3.237	3.281	-2.063	17985	[-0.086; -0.002]	** / *
PF1	4.325	4.208	5.372	18036	[0.075; 0.160]	*** / ***
PF2	4.308	4.187	5.490	18035	[0.078; 0.164]	*** / ***
PA1	4.168	4.101	2.962	18036	[0.023; 0.111]	*** / ***
PA2	3.949	3.898	2.177	18031	[0.005; 0.099]	** / *
PC1	3.323	3.373	-2.213	18039	[-0.094; -0.006]	** / **
PC2	4.156	4.060	4.155	18040	[0.051; 0.142]	*** / ***
Tr1	4.275	4.130	6.432	18040	[0.101; 0.189]	*** / ***
Tr2	4.461	4.349	5.248	18032	[0.070; 0.155]	*** / ***
PU1	4.120	4.014	4.681	18039	[0.062; 0.151]	*** / ***
PU2	4.149	4.058	3.921	18040	[0.045; 0.136]	*** / ***
Attitudes (Sum)	47.895	47.083	4.841	18027	[0.483; 1.140]	*** / ***
Attitudes (PCA)	0.042	-0.042	5.687	18028	[0.055; 0.114]	*** / ***

Notes: Significance levels: * $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$. “Welch” refers to two-sample t -tests with unequal variances; “Wilc.” refers to Wilcoxon rank-sum tests.

Providing respondents with an explanation of how the systems operate shifts several attitudinal dimensions in a more favorable direction (Table 3). The most consistent gains appear for fairness, trust, and usefulness: both fairness items increase by about 0.12 points (PF1: 4.325 vs 4.208; PF2: 4.308 vs 4.187), and trust and usefulness rise by roughly 0.09–0.15 points (Tr1: 4.275 vs 4.130; Tr2: 4.461 vs 4.349; PU1: 4.120 vs 4.014; PU2: 4.149 vs 4.058). These differences are statistically significant under both the Welch and Wilcoxon tests. Privacy-related responses move in opposite directions across items: PC2 increases (4.156 vs 4.060), while PC1 declines slightly (3.323 vs 3.373), consistent with modest re-weighting rather than uniform shifts in privacy concerns.

By contrast, transparency concerns are largely unaffected. TC1 is essentially unchanged (3.424 vs 3.426), and TC2 decreases only marginally (3.237 vs 3.281), with weaker support under the rank-sum test. At the aggregate level, the overall attitude sum rises from 47.083 in the baseline group to 47.895 in the treated group, and the PCA-based attitude index shifts from -0.042 to 0.042 . Substantively, these effects are precisely estimated but modest relative to the 1–7 scale, typically on the order of one-tenth of a point for individual items.

4.1.3 Willingness to delegate

We distinguish between weak delegation—willingness to use the system as an assistive tool (WTD1)—and strong delegation—willingness to cede decision rights and let the system decide (WTD2). Willingness to

Table 4: Treated vs Baseline: Welch two-sample t -tests and Wilcoxon rank-sum tests

Variable	Mean (Treated)	Mean (Baseline)	t	df	95% CI (diff)	Sig. (Welch / Wilc.)
WTD1 (Weak)	4.21	4.10	4.76	18040	[0.07; 0.16]	*** / ***
WTD2 (Strong)	3.77	3.71	2.06	18034	[0.00; 0.10]	** / *

Notes: Significance levels: * $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$. “Welch” refers to two-sample t -tests with unequal variances; “Wilc.” refers to Wilcoxon rank-sum tests.

delegate is systematically higher under weak than strong delegation in both groups, consistent with greater comfort with advisory or limited delegation than with fully automated decision-making (Figures 24–25). Pooling across systems, the treatment increases weak delegation from 4.10 in the baseline group to 4.21 in the treated group (Table 4), a difference of 0.11 points (95% CI [0.07; 0.16]) that is strongly significant under both Welch and Wilcoxon tests. For strong delegation, the corresponding gap is smaller—3.71 to 3.77 (CI [0.00; 0.10]), and the evidence is weaker: it is significant under Welch at conventional levels but only marginal under Wilcoxon. Overall, the informational treatment produces precisely estimated but modest changes in delegation preferences, concentrated on the weaker form of delegation.

Heterogeneity across systems mirrors this aggregate pattern. Delegation is highest in domains where algorithmic assistance is perceived as routine or beneficial (e.g., *Search Engines* and *Healthcare Diagnosis*) and lowest for *Online Advertising*, especially under strong delegation (Figures 24–25).

4.2 Empirical Strategy

Our experiment randomly assigns respondents to either (i) a short definition of each system (control) or (ii) the same definition plus a brief explanation of how the system works (treatment). Each respondent evaluates multiple systems, so the data have a repeated-measures structure: respondent i provides outcomes for system s . We ask two related questions. First, does the explanation affect (i) beliefs, (ii) evaluative attitudes, and (iii) willingness to delegate? Second, to what extent are the observed effects consistent with a simple sequential mechanism?

We posit that brief procedural explanations can influence delegation preferences through the following sequential pathway:

$$\text{Explanation} \rightarrow \text{Beliefs} \rightarrow \text{Attitudes} \rightarrow \text{Delegation}.$$

In our setting, “beliefs” refer to respondents’ system-specific subjective perceptions. In particular, their perceived familiarity, knowledge, use, and exposure to the system were elicited immediately after the vignette (definition with or without explanation) and before the attitude and delegation items. We interpret these measures as respondents’ perceived understanding of the system at the time of elicitation; they may reflect both pre-existing views and any updating induced by the informational content.

A complication is that beliefs and attitudes are elicited after treatment exposure and may therefore lie

on the causal path from the explanation to downstream outcomes. Conditioning on beliefs in an attitude regression would amount to controlling for a post-treatment mediator, shifting the estimand away from the total effect of treatment on attitudes toward a direct effect that holds the mediator fixed. For clarity, we therefore proceed in two complementary steps: we first estimate reduced-form (total) treatment effects on each outcome block, and we then implement a recursive three-equation system as a mechanism-consistent decomposition that quantifies the extent to which treatment effects on delegation are consistent with pathways operating through beliefs and/or attitudes. This approach follows the logic of path analysis (Wright, 1921) and the classic product-of-coefficients decomposition used in mediation research (Baron & Kenny, 1986), adapted to a multilevel setting with repeated measures (Bauer et al., 2006). We treat the decomposition as descriptive of plausible pathways rather than as definitive causal mediation, consistent with modern discussions of identification in mediation analysis (Imai et al., 2010).

Variables and structure We work with standardized (z-scored) versions of three outcome blocks: B_{is}^z (a beliefs index), A_{is}^z (an attitude index), and D_{is}^z (willingness to delegate). The beliefs index aggregates respondents’ subjective beliefs about the system (e.g., perceived familiarity, self-assessed knowledge, perceived exposure, and self-reported use). Because each respondent evaluates multiple systems, we include a respondent random intercept ($1 | i$) to account for within-respondent dependence. We also include system fixed effects (12 systems) and pre-treatment covariates,

$$X_i = \{\text{Country, Age, Gender, Marital status, Education, Employment status, Income}\}.$$

Step 1: Does treatment change beliefs? We first estimate:

$$B_{is}^z = \alpha_s + a T_{is} + X_i' \pi + u_i + \varepsilon_{is}^B. \quad (1)$$

The coefficient a captures the effect of the explanation on beliefs (in standard deviation units).

Step 2: Are attitudes associated with beliefs, and does treatment still matter? Next we estimate:

$$A_{is}^z = \beta_s + c T_{is} + b B_{is}^z + X_i' \lambda + v_i + \varepsilon_{is}^A. \quad (2)$$

In this equation, b captures the association between beliefs and attitudes, while c captures any remaining treatment association with attitudes conditional on beliefs. As noted above, we do not interpret c as replacing the reduced-form (total) effect of treatment on attitudes; rather, it is part of the mechanism-consistent decomposition (Baron & Kenny, 1986; Bauer et al., 2006).

Step 3: Does delegation covary with attitudes and beliefs, and is there any remaining direct treatment effect? Finally, we estimate:

$$D_{is}^z = \gamma_s + d T_{is} + f A_{is}^z + e B_{is}^z + X_i' \mu + w_i + \varepsilon_{is}^D. \quad (3)$$

Here f captures the association between attitudes and delegation, e captures the association between beliefs and delegation, and d captures any remaining treatment association with delegation conditional on attitudes and beliefs.

Turning the three regressions into a decomposition Let \hat{a} be the estimated coefficient on T from (1), \hat{b} and \hat{c} the coefficients on B^z and T from (2), and $\hat{d}, \hat{e}, \hat{f}$ the coefficients on T, B^z , and A^z from (3). In a linear model, the standard product-of-coefficients logic yields the following components (Baron & Kenny, 1986; Bauer et al., 2006):

$$\text{Direct (not via } A \text{ or } B): \quad \hat{d}, \quad (4)$$

$$\text{Indirect via perceived understanding (} T \rightarrow B \rightarrow D \text{):} \quad \hat{a}\hat{e}, \quad (5)$$

$$\text{Indirect via attitudes (} T \rightarrow A \rightarrow D \text{):} \quad \hat{c}\hat{f}, \quad (6)$$

$$\text{Indirect via perceived understanding and attitudes (} T \rightarrow B \rightarrow A \rightarrow D \text{):} \quad \hat{a}\hat{b}\hat{f}, \quad (7)$$

$$\text{Total (sum of components):} \quad \hat{d} + \hat{a}\hat{e} + \hat{c}\hat{f} + \hat{a}\hat{b}\hat{f}. \quad (8)$$

Interpretation. In a linear recursive system, the sum of the four components equals the model-implied total effect of T on delegation D ; because T is randomly assigned, this total (reduced-form) effect is causal. By contrast, the allocation of that total across components relies on modeling assumptions and is not interpreted as causal mediation without additional identification conditions.

In linear systems, indirect effects follow the product-of-coefficients rule: a one-unit change in T shifts B by \hat{a} , and each unit increase in B shifts D by \hat{e} , implying an indirect effect $\hat{a}\hat{e}$; analogous reasoning yields $\hat{c}\hat{f}$ and $\hat{a}\hat{b}\hat{f}$ for longer paths. This decomposition maps directly onto our conceptual sequence: explanations may affect delegation directly, indirectly by increasing perceived understanding, indirectly by shifting attitudes, and indirectly through a sequential pathway from perceived understanding to attitudes to delegation.

Following Imai et al. (2010), this product-of-coefficients decomposition coincides with a causal mediation estimated in linear models under sequential ignorability and an additional no-treatment–mediator–interaction assumption (so that mediation effects do not vary with treatment status). Accordingly, we treat the resulting components as mechanism-consistent accounting terms and emphasize total (reduced-form) treatment effects as our primary causal estimates.

Uncertainty: respondent-level bootstrap Because the indirect effects are products of estimated coefficients, we do not rely on standard closed-form variance formulas. Instead, we obtain uncertainty estimates via a respondent-level bootstrap designed to respect the repeated-measures structure of the data (Bauer et al., 2006). Specifically, we repeatedly resample respondents with replacement and, for each resampled respondent, retain all associated system-level observations. For each bootstrap replicate, we re-estimate the three mixed-effects models, recompute the direct, indirect, and total components implied by the decomposition, and use the resulting empirical sampling distribution to construct percentile confidence intervals based

on the 2.5th and 97.5th percentiles.

Interpretation note The recursive system should be read as an *accounting device* rather than as a stand-alone causal claim about mediation. The reduced-form regressions identify the *total* effect of the explanation on each outcome because treatment is randomly assigned. By contrast, once we include post-treatment variables such as beliefs (B_{is}^z) and attitudes (A_{is}^z) on the right-hand side (e.g., when modeling attitudes as a function of beliefs, or delegation as a function of attitudes and beliefs), the corresponding coefficients do not automatically admit a causal interpretation. The reason is that beliefs and attitudes are not randomized: even though they are influenced by treatment, they may also be jointly shaped by unobserved respondent-specific factors (e.g., general optimism about technology, baseline trust, political orientation, or response styles) that also affect delegation. If such unobserved factors exist, then the associations $B \rightarrow A$ and $A \rightarrow D$ in the system may reflect both causal effects and residual confounding.

Interpreting the product terms (e.g., \widehat{abf}) as *causal* indirect effects therefore requires additional assumptions beyond treatment randomization. In the potential-outcomes framework, a common sufficient condition is *sequential ignorability*: conditional on treatment and observed pre-treatment covariates, there are no unobserved confounders of the mediator–outcome relationship (and, in the sequential case, no unobserved confounders of the relationship between earlier and later mediators). These assumptions are strong and cannot be tested directly; modern mediation work emphasizes reporting them transparently and, when possible, assessing sensitivity to violations (Imai et al., 2010).

For this reason, we interpret the decomposition in a deliberately modest way: it quantifies how much of the treatment effect on delegation is consistent with pathways operating through beliefs and attitudes under a linear approximation, and it provides a structured summary that helps connect the empirical results to our theoretical sequence. We continue to treat the reduced-form treatment effects as the primary causal estimates, and we treat the decomposition as complementary evidence about plausible channels.

4.3 Treatment Effect

4.3.1 Decomposing the treatment effect on delegation

We examine whether the experimental effect of explanations on willingness to delegate can be summarized by a simple sequential structure, in which explanations shift respondents’ beliefs about a system, which in turn shape their attitudes and ultimately influence their delegation. Table 5 reports the resulting decomposition using sum-based indices for beliefs and attitudes, while Table 6 replicates the exercise using PCA-based indices. Throughout, outcomes are standardized, so coefficients are expressed in standard deviation units.

Two patterns stand out. First, the estimated direct component of treatment on delegation is small and statistically indistinguishable from zero for both the weak (WTD1) and strong (WTD2) delegation measures. In contrast, the total treatment effect is positive and precisely estimated for both outcomes: explanations increase WTD1 by 0.094 SD and WTD2 by 0.062 SD when using sum indices (Table 5). The same qualitative

Table 5: Decomposition of Treatment Effects on Willingness to Delegate (Sum Indices)

	<i>Dependent variable:</i>	
	Willingness to Delegate	
	WTD1 (Weak)	WTD2 (Strong)
	(1)	(2)
Direct (\widehat{d})	-0.002 (0.010)	-0.015 (0.014)
Indirect via beliefs (\widehat{ae})	0.016*** (0.003)	0.006*** (0.001)
Indirect via attitudes (\widehat{cf})	0.064*** (0.015)	0.057*** (0.013)
Indirect via beliefs \rightarrow attitudes (\widehat{abf})	0.015*** (0.003)	0.014*** (0.002)
Total	0.094*** (0.020)	0.062*** (0.022)
Observations	18042	18042
Respondents	3007	3007
Bootstrap replications	500	500

Note: Entries report respondent-level cluster bootstrap means with bootstrap standard errors in parentheses (500 replications). Outcomes are standardized (z-scores), so effects are in SD units. The beliefs index (B^z) and the attitude index (A^z) are constructed as *sum scores* of their respective item batteries and then standardized. Stars are based on bootstrap two-sided p -values. * $p < 0.1$; ** $p < 0.05$; *** $p < 0.01$

conclusions are obtained with PCA-based indices (Table 6), indicating that the decomposition is not sensitive to the specific index construction.

Second, the increase in delegation is primarily consistent with pathways operating through respondents' attitudes. In the sum-index specification, the indirect component operating through attitudes only ($T \rightarrow A \rightarrow D$) accounts for 0.064 SD in WTD1 and 0.057 SD in WTD2, making it the largest single component. A further, smaller but statistically significant component operates through a sequential pathway in which treatment shifts beliefs, beliefs shape attitudes, and attitudes in turn predict delegation ($T \rightarrow B \rightarrow A \rightarrow D$): 0.015 SD for WTD1 and 0.014 SD for WTD2. The remaining indirect pathway operating through beliefs without attitudes ($T \rightarrow B \rightarrow D$) is positive but comparatively modest (0.016 SD for WTD1 and 0.006

Table 6: Decomposition of Treatment Effects on Willingness to Delegate (PCA indices)

	<i>Dependent variable:</i>	
	Willingness to Delegate	
	WTD1 (Weak)	WTD2 (Strong)
	(1)	(2)
Direct (\widehat{d})	0.008 (0.010)	-0.015 (0.014)
Indirect via beliefs (\widehat{ae})	0.010*** (0.002)	0.006*** (0.001)
Indirect via attitudes (\widehat{cf})	0.056*** (0.015)	0.057*** (0.013)
Indirect via beliefs \rightarrow attitudes (\widehat{abf})	0.019*** (0.004)	0.014*** (0.002)
Total	0.094*** (0.020)	0.062*** (0.022)
Observations	18042	18042
Respondents	3007	3007
Bootstrap replications	500	500

Note: Entries report respondent-level cluster bootstrap means with bootstrap standard errors in parentheses (500 replications). Outcomes are standardized (z-scores), so effects are in SD units. The beliefs index (B^z) and attitude index (A^z) are constructed using principal component analysis (PCA) and then standardized. Stars are based on bootstrap two-sided p -values. * $p < 0.1$; ** $p < 0.05$; *** $p < 0.01$.

SD for WTD2). Taken together, these results suggest that explanations increase delegation mainly to the extent that they improve evaluative attitudes toward the systems, with beliefs playing a supporting role by contributing to attitude change.

The PCA specification mirrors this pattern closely. The attitudes-only pathway remains the dominant contributor (0.056 SD for WTD1 and 0.057 SD for WTD2), while the sequential beliefs-to-attitudes pathway is of similar magnitude (0.019 SD and 0.014 SD, respectively). The beliefs-only component remains positive but small (0.010 SD for WTD1 and 0.006 SD for WTD2). Across both constructions, therefore, the decomposition implies that explanations primarily matter because they shift evaluative judgments of the systems, rather than because they generate a sizable residual direct propensity to delegate once beliefs and attitudes

are taken into account.

Expressed as shares of the total effect (sum-index specification), the attitudes-only pathway $T \rightarrow A \rightarrow D$ accounts for roughly two-thirds of the WTD1 total (0.064 of 0.094) and the vast majority of the WTD2 total (0.057 of 0.062), with the remaining positive contribution split across the beliefs-only and sequential pathways; because the estimated direct component is slightly negative for WTD2, component shares can exceed 100% in absolute value and are therefore interpreted descriptively.

To aid interpretation, we translate standardized effects back to the original 1–7 scale. Using the sample standard deviations ($SD(WTD1) = 1.582$, $SD(WTD2) = 1.676$), the total treatment effect corresponds to an increase of approximately 0.15 points on WTD1 ($0.094 SD \times 1.582$) and 0.10 points on WTD2 ($0.062 SD \times 1.676$). Relative to the sample means ($mean(WTD1) = 4.16$, $mean(WTD2) = 3.74$), these shifts amount to about 3.6% and 2.8%, respectively. The largest component operates through attitudes: the $T \rightarrow A \rightarrow D$ pathway corresponds to roughly 0.10 points on WTD1 and 0.096 points on WTD2 on the original scale. As a diagnostic, we verify that both in the pooled sample and system-by-system, the sum of the four estimated components equals the reduced-form treatment effect of T on delegation (up to numerical tolerance), as implied by the linear recursive system.

Figure 1: Decomposition per system, WTD1 (Weak)

4.3.2 Heterogeneity across systems

Figures 1 and 2, together with Appendix Tables 22 and 23, show the same decomposition estimated separately for each system; we treat these system-level results as exploratory heterogeneity patterns (without adjusting for multiple comparisons). For WTD1, the explanation increases willingness to delegate for a subset of systems, with especially large total effects for predictive policing (total ≈ 0.27 SD, about 0.43 points on the 7-point scale) and healthcare diagnosis (total ≈ 0.20 SD, about 0.32 points). Positive and statistically significant totals also appear for algorithmic trading, online advertising, job applications, and recommendation systems (totals roughly between 0.11 and 0.18 SD; about 0.18–0.29 points). For the remaining systems (e.g., robo-advisors, search engines, social media), total effects are smaller and typically not statistically distinguishable from zero.

For WTD2 (strong delegation), the pattern is similar but attenuated: significant total effects are concentrated in fewer systems and are generally smaller in magnitude. The strongest and most robust positive total effects appear for online advertising (total ≈ 0.18 SD, about 0.30 points) and job applications (total ≈ 0.13 SD, about 0.22 points), with healthcare diagnosis also showing a positive total effect (total ≈ 0.16 SD, about 0.27 points). Across many other systems, totals are close to zero and imprecisely estimated.

As a formal test of treatment-effect heterogeneity across the 12 systems, we compared a model with a common treatment effect to a model allowing the treatment effect to vary by system via a full $T \times \text{System}$ interaction. Likelihood-ratio tests show that adding the interaction does not improve fit for either outcome (WTD1: $\chi^2(11)=13.38$, $p=0.27$; WTD2: $\chi^2(11)=10.53$, $p=0.48$). Thus, we find no statistical evidence that the explanation effect on willingness to delegate differs systematically across systems in this specification.

4.3.3 Which components account for system-level effects?

Across systems where the total effect is statistically detectable, the decomposition consistently attributes most of the increase in delegation to attitude-related components. The indirect component operating through attitudes $T \rightarrow A \rightarrow D$ is frequently the largest single term, and it is often complemented by a positive sequential component $T \rightarrow B \rightarrow A \rightarrow D$. By contrast, the direct component is rarely distinguishable from zero at the system level (and when it is, it is typically smaller than the attitude-related terms), consistent with the interpretation that explanations affect delegation primarily by shifting evaluative attitudes rather than by changing delegation “directly.”

Finally, comparing the appendix tables for sum versus PCA constructions shows that the total effects are stable across index choices, while the allocation across belief-based components is somewhat more sensitive to how beliefs are summarized (and can change in magnitude, and occasionally sign, depending on the index construction).

Overall, explanations increase delegation primarily by shifting evaluative attitudes, while changes in perceived understanding matter mainly insofar as they contribute to attitude change. The pooled results establish that explanations increase perceived understanding and improve several evaluative attitudes, with

Figure 2: Decomposition per system, WTD2 (Strong)

modest downstream effects on delegation. We next unpack (i) which specific items drive these average patterns and (ii) whether effects are systematically stronger in certain domains or for certain respondents.

4.4 Heterogeneity and additional analyses

4.4.1 Item-level effects

To complement the index-based results in the main text, Figure 3 reports *item-level* treatment marginal gains of providing an explanation. For each belief and attitude item, we estimate a pooled linear mixed model of the form $Y_{is} = \theta T_{is} + \alpha_s + X_i' \pi + u_i + \varepsilon_{is}$, including system fixed effects, the same pre-treatment covariates as in the main specifications, and a respondent random intercept. Coefficients are expressed in points on the original 1–7 response scale. Statistical significance is based on respondent-clustered standard errors.³ Transparency Concerns 1–2 and Privacy Concerns 1 are reverse-coded so that positive coefficients always indicate a shift in a more favorable direction.

Two patterns mirror the main findings. First, explanations generate clear gains in belief-related items. All four belief measures increase significantly, with the largest effect on self-reported use (U1: +0.245 points), followed by perceived exposure (EXP1: +0.181), and the two knowledge and familiarity items (K1: +0.159;

³Specifically, inference uses cluster-robust standard errors at the respondent level, so that statistical uncertainty is robust to within-respondent correlation beyond what is captured by the random intercept.

Figure 3: Item-level marginal gains of explanations

K2: +0.149). Thus, explanations substantially increase respondents’ perceived understanding and subjective engagement with the systems.

Second, explanations primarily improve evaluative attitudes tied to fairness, trust, accountability, and usefulness, while having a limited impact on transparency and (one dimension of) privacy. Fairness increases by about +0.143 (PF1) to +0.160 (PF2) points; trust increases by +0.150 (Tr2) to +0.191 (Tr1) points; and usefulness increases by +0.133 (PU2) to +0.148 (PU1) points. Accountability also rises modestly (PA1: +0.106; PA2: +0.109). By contrast, the transparency items remain statistically indistinguishable from zero (TC1: +0.021; TC2: -0.033), consistent with the descriptive results showing that explanations do not materially alleviate transparency concerns. For privacy, the “assurance” item (PC2) increases (+0.144), whereas the item capturing concern about personal information use (PC1) shows essentially no change (+0.011).

Overall, the item-level evidence reinforces the interpretation from the decomposition: explanations reliably increase perceived understanding and improve key evaluative attitudes (especially trust, fairness, and usefulness), while leaving transparency concerns largely unaffected. These patterns help clarify which specific components of the beliefs and attitudes batteries account for the positive, but modest, downstream increase in willingness to delegate reported in the main results.

4.4.2 Heterogeneity by baseline familiarity

Figure 4: Conditional marginal gains of explanations by baseline system familiarity.

A natural question is whether explanations generate larger marginal gains for systems that are initially less familiar to respondents (i.e., whether informational returns diminish with baseline familiarity). Because individual self-reported familiarity is measured post-treatment and is itself affected by the explanation, we avoid conditioning on respondents' own familiarity scores. Instead, we use a system-level proxy for

baseline familiarity that is computed exclusively in the control group: for each system, we take the mean of the familiarity item (K2) among untreated respondents and standardize this measure across systems. We then estimate, separately for each survey item, a mixed-effects specification interacting treatment with this baseline familiarity proxy, controlling for system fixed effects, respondent covariates, and a respondent random intercept. Inference uses respondent-clustered standard errors.

In the control group, baseline system familiarity is highest for *Search Engines* ($z = 1.72$), *Social Media* ($z = 1.42$), and *Recommendation* systems ($z = 0.92$), and lowest for *Predictive Policing* ($z = -1.62$) and *Algorithmic Trading* ($z = -1.02$). Systems with above-average baseline familiarity ($z > 0$) include *Search Engines*, *Social Media*, *Recommendation*, *Online Advertising*, and *Insurance Premium*, whereas the remaining systems have below-average baseline familiarity ($z < 0$).

Figure 4 reports the implied conditional treatment effects evaluated at low baseline familiarity (-1 SD) and high baseline familiarity ($+1$ SD). Two patterns emerge. First, explanations increase most belief and evaluative attitude items in both contexts. The largest and most consistent gains appear for perceived fairness, accountability, trust, and usefulness: for instance, fairness items increase by about 0.12–0.20 points, trust by about 0.13–0.22 points, and usefulness by about 0.10–0.20 points, depending on the baseline familiarity level. By contrast, transparency items remain close to zero (TC1 and TC2 both have confidence intervals spanning zero at both low and high familiarity), and privacy concerns show mixed results: PC2 increases modestly and positively, while PC1 remains near zero.

Second, while the point estimates sometimes differ between low and high baseline familiarity, the evidence for systematic moderation is limited. For most items, the conditional effects at -1 SD and $+1$ SD are of similar magnitude and overlap substantially. This is also true for delegation outcomes: both WTD1 and WTD2 are positive at low and high familiarity, but the differences across familiarity levels are not large relative to uncertainty (WTD1: 0.18 vs. 0.12; WTD2: 0.13 vs. 0.07, with the high-familiarity WTD2 interval including zero).

Overall, these exploratory results suggest broadly positive marginal gains of explanations across beliefs and several attitude dimensions, with little clear evidence that returns systematically diminish (or increase) with baseline system familiarity. Where differences appear, they tend to be modest and item-specific rather than a general pattern across constructs.

4.4.3 Heterogeneity by political preferences

Explanations may be processed through broader worldviews about technology, institutions, and regulation. We therefore explore whether the treatment effect differs by respondents’ political self-placement, as a parsimonious proxy for such latent predispositions. The political self-placement item (S10) is collapsed into four groups: *Left* (Left-wing/Progressive, Center-left, Green/Environmentalist), *Center* (Centrist/Moderate), *Right* (Center-right, Right-wing/Conservative, Nationalist/Populist), and *Non-aligned/Other* (Libertarian, Other, None/Not affiliated, Prefer not to say). The resulting respondent counts are: Left ($n = 863$), Center

Figure 5: Treatment effects by political group

($n = 280$), Right ($n = 1024$), and Non-aligned/Other ($n = 840$). Treatment assignment is balanced within groups.

We estimate mixed-effects models of willingness to delegate (WTD1 and WTD2) with respondent random intercepts, system fixed effects, and the standard demographic controls, allowing the treatment effect to vary by political group via a treatment-by-group interaction. Likelihood-ratio tests indicate no detectable heterogeneity for weak delegation (WTD1: $\chi^2(3) = 4.06$, $p = 0.255$), but evidence of heterogeneity for strong delegation (WTD2: $\chi^2(3) = 10.85$, $p = 0.013$).

To summarize subgroup-specific effects, we report treatment-control contrasts within each political group. Inference is based on respondent-clustered robust standard errors to account for within-respondent dependence induced by the repeated-measures design. For WTD1, explanations increase willingness to delegate among right-leaning respondents ($= 0.313$, $SE = 0.060$, 95% CI [0.194, 0.431], $p < 0.001$) and also among

left-leaning respondents ($= 0.154$, $SE= 0.064$, $95\% \text{ CI } [0.028, 0.279]$, $p = 0.017$). Effects for centrist respondents are imprecisely estimated (estimate $= 0.155$, $SE= 0.111$, $95\% \text{ CI } [-0.064, 0.373]$), and estimates for the non-aligned/other group are close to zero ($= -0.057$, $SE= 0.070$, $95\% \text{ CI } [-0.195, 0.081]$).

For WTD2, the treatment effect is concentrated among right-leaning respondents ($= 0.282$, $SE= 0.067$, $95\% \text{ CI } [0.151, 0.413]$, $p < 0.001$), while effects in the Left, Center, and Non-aligned/Other groups are small and statistically indistinguishable from zero. Overall, these exploratory results suggest that explanations increase willingness to delegate primarily among respondents on the political right, with more limited evidence of an effect for weak delegation among left-leaning respondents.

4.4.4 Heterogeneity by attention

Figure 6: Attention to the explanation and willingness to delegate, pooled

A natural interpretation of the treatment is that it operates through comprehension of the procedural

content. We therefore examine whether treatment effects are larger among treated respondents who correctly answer two comprehension questions. Because the attention-check questions are only asked in the treated condition, control respondents cannot “pass” by construction. We therefore re-parameterize treatment into a three-level indicator: *Control*, *Treated (fail)*, and *Treated (pass)* (pass = 1 if both questions are answered correctly). We estimate pooled mixed-effects models with system fixed effects, the standard demographic controls, and respondent random intercepts, and compute cluster-robust standard errors clustered at the respondent level.

Figure 6 reports the implied contrasts for weak (WTD1) and strong (WTD2) delegation. For WTD1, explanations increase willingness to delegate among treated respondents who fail the attention check relative to the control group (Treated (fail) – Control: 0.119, SE = 0.046, $p = 0.010$). Importantly, respondents who pass the attention check exhibit an additional increase relative to treated failers (Treated (pass) – Treated (fail): 0.058, SE = 0.026, $p = 0.028$), yielding a larger overall effect for passers relative to controls (Treated (pass) – Control: 0.177, SE = 0.047, $p < 0.001$).

For WTD2, the treatment effect is weaker and less precisely estimated. Treated failers are only marginally higher than controls (Treated (fail) – Control: 0.094, SE = 0.050, $p = 0.061$). Passing the attention check does not generate an additional gain beyond treated failers (Treated (pass) – Treated (fail): 0.018, SE = 0.026, $p = 0.503$), although passers still differ positively from controls overall (Treated (pass) – Control: 0.112, SE = 0.051, $p = 0.027$).

These patterns suggest that attention to the explanatory content is associated with a larger increase in weak delegation, while differences between passers and failers are not detectable for strong delegation. As with the other exploratory analyses, these comparisons should be interpreted descriptively rather than as causal effects of “paying attention,” since attention-check performance is not randomly assigned. These comparisons quantify how the treatment effect varies with an observed post-treatment marker of comprehension, rather than the causal effect of comprehension itself.

We next replicate this analysis separately by system by interacting the three-level comprehension indicator (Control, Treated–fail, Treated–pass) allowing the 3-level indicator effects to vary by system, and we report three contrasts within each system: (i) Treated (fail) - Control, (ii) Treated (pass) - Treated (fail), and (iii) Treated (pass) - Control. Figure 7 displays point estimates and 95% confidence intervals using respondent-clustered standard errors. Because these comparisons are exploratory and numerous (12 systems \times 3 contrasts \times 2 outcomes), we interpret patterns qualitatively and treat conventional p -values as descriptive.

For weak delegation (WTD1), the treated–control gaps are positive in many systems, but the magnitude varies substantially. The largest “Treated (pass) - Control” effects occur for Predictive Policing (+0.493) and Recommendation (+0.314), and are also sizable for Job Applications (+0.273). Several additional systems show more modest positive effects (e.g., Algorithmic Trading and Credit Scoring). Differences between treated passers and treated failers are only statistically distinguishable from zero in a small subset

Figure 7: Attention to the explanation and willingness to delegate, by system

of systems. In particular, passers report significantly higher willingness to delegate than failers for Predictive Policing (+0.332) and Recommendation (+0.280), suggesting that better comprehension is associated with greater acceptance in these domains. By contrast, Online Advertising exhibits the opposite pattern: while Treated (fail) exceeds Control (+0.259), Treated (pass) is not reliably above Control (+0.125) because the “pass-fail” contrast is negative (-0.134).

For strong delegation (WTD2), effects are more selective and generally less precisely estimated. The clearest positive “Treated (pass) - Control” contrasts appear for Predictive Policing (+0.309) and Job Applications (+0.296). As with WTD1, the “pass-fail” contrast is positive for Predictive Policing (+0.319), while it is negative for Online Advertising (-0.214) and Social Media (-0.183). In both of these latter systems, treated failers are above (or marginally above) controls, whereas passers are approximately indistinguishable from controls, consistent with the idea that a more complete understanding may attenuate willingness to

fully delegate in advertising- and social-media contexts.

Overall, the system-level results suggest that the relationship between comprehension and delegation is not uniform across domains: passing the attention check is associated with substantially higher willingness to delegate for some systems (most notably predictive policing and recommendation), but not for others, where better comprehension may instead coincide with greater caution (online advertising and social media).

4.5 Summary of results

Across the 12 algorithmic domains, providing respondents with a brief explanation of how each system works produces clear and consistent shifts in subjective beliefs, more modest improvements in evaluative attitudes, and small but detectable increases in willingness to delegate.

Descriptive patterns. In the baseline condition, beliefs and delegation vary substantially across systems. Everyday digital technologies (e.g., search engines and social media) are rated highest on familiarity, exposure, and use, whereas institutionally distant applications (e.g., predictive policing) score lowest. Attitudes are mildly favorable on average, especially for fairness, trust, and usefulness, while transparency remains the least favorable dimension.

Reduced-form treatment effects. Pooling across systems, explanations significantly increase all belief items—knowledge, familiarity, perceived exposure, and self-reported use—by roughly 0.15 to 0.25 points on the 1–7 scale. Attitudinal effects are positive but smaller and concentrated in fairness, trust, usefulness, and (to a lesser extent) accountability; transparency concerns remain essentially unchanged, and privacy responses are mixed across items. Delegation rises modestly: weak delegation increases more reliably than strong delegation.

Mechanism-consistent decomposition. A recursive three-equation decomposition indicates that the total treatment effect on delegation is primarily consistent with pathways operating through attitudes. The direct treatment component is close to zero, while most of the increase in both weak and strong delegation is accounted for by (i) an attitudes-only pathway and (ii) a smaller sequential pathway from beliefs to attitudes to delegation. These conclusions are robust to constructing beliefs and attitudes indices either as sums or via PCA.

Exploratory heterogeneity. Item-level estimates confirm that belief gains are largest for perceived exposure and self-reported use, and that evaluative improvements are concentrated in fairness, trust, and usefulness. Using a control-group proxy for baseline system familiarity, conditional effects are broadly positive at both low and high familiarity, with limited evidence of systematic moderation. Political heterogeneity is more pronounced for strong delegation: effects are concentrated among right-leaning respondents, whereas weak delegation increases among right-leaning respondents and more modestly among left-leaning respondents. Finally, using an attention-check measure asked only in the treated condition, delegation increases even among treated respondents who fail the check, while passing the check is associated with an additional gain for weak delegation (but not for strong delegation) in the pooled analysis; system-specific patterns are

heterogeneous, with larger pass–fail gaps in some domains (e.g., predictive policing and recommendation) and negative gaps in others (e.g., online advertising and social media). Because these heterogeneity analyses rely on post-treatment subgrouping and many comparisons, they are interpreted descriptively.

Taken together, the results show that brief explanations reliably increase perceived understanding and improve several evaluative attitudes, and that these attitudinal shifts account for most of the modest downstream increase in willingness to delegate.

5 Conclusion

Algorithmic decision-making systems increasingly mediate access to jobs, credit, insurance, public services, and information. In Europe, this shift is occurring alongside an expanding legal architecture that explicitly ties the legitimacy of algorithmic decision-making to information disclosure and transparency requirements.⁴ Yet an economically salient empirical question remains: when individuals receive an explanation that regulators could realistically mandate at scale, do they update beliefs and attitudes in ways that translate into adoption and delegation?

We answer this question with a large survey experiment in three major EU countries (France, Germany, and Italy; $N = 3007$; Section ??). The design deliberately targets a policy-relevant margin. All respondents receive a neutral description of what a system is used for; the treatment adds a short, non-technical explanation of how it works. Because each respondent evaluates multiple algorithmic domains, we can compare reactions across contexts while holding fixed individual traits, and we can distinguish “weak” delegation (using the system as decision support) from “strong” delegation (ceding decision rights).

Three results stand out. First, explanations generate large and robust shifts in perceived familiarity and experience. Relative to the baseline, treated respondents report higher knowledge, familiarity, exposure, and self-reported use (Table 2), with average differences on the order of 0.2–0.5 points on a 7-point scale. This is consistent with a central premise from information economics: even simple disclosures can relax informational frictions by helping people form a more concrete mental model of an otherwise more opaque technology.

Second, explanations improve a broad set of evaluative attitudes that are central to both policy debates and adoption decisions. Pooling across domains, the treatment increases perceived fairness, accountability, trust, and usefulness, and it modestly shifts privacy-related responses (Table 3). Transparency itself appears harder to move: one transparency item is essentially unaffected, and the other shifts slightly in the opposite direction, suggesting that brief descriptions of “how it works” may raise standards for what respondents consider genuinely transparent. Put differently, disclosure can improve perceived legitimacy along several margins while still leaving a residual “opacity” concern: a pattern that is highly relevant for policy designs that equate disclosure with transparency.

⁴See the EU AI Act (Regulation (EU) 2024/1689) and the Digital Services Act (Regulation (EU) 2022/2065).

Third, explanations increase willingness to delegate, but the effect is modest and concentrated in weak delegation. Average willingness to use the system as assistance rises by about 0.11 points, while willingness to cede decision rights rises by roughly 0.06 points (Table 4). This gap matters economically: it implies that the behavioral margin most responsive to realistic disclosures is complementarity between humans and algorithms (support), rather than full substitution (automation). In a European context where institutional legitimacy and accountability constraints are salient, this distinction helps reconcile why transparency mandates may increase acceptance without producing blanket enthusiasm for “turning decisions over” to machines.

In addition to providing these tractable statistical estimates, our mechanism-consistent decomposition reinforces an economic interpretation of these patterns. The direct effect of receiving an explanation on delegation is close to zero, while the total effect is largely mediated through updated beliefs and, especially, through updated evaluative attitudes (Table 5). This structure is informative for both theory and policy: disclosures appear to work less by mechanically “persuading” respondents and more by shifting the perceived trade-offs that underpin adoption decisions (e.g., usefulness versus privacy concern, or fairness and accountability versus opacity).

The cross-domain nature of the study also highlights a key takeaway for European governance: public acceptance is not unidimensional. Even under a standardized disclosure, the responsiveness of beliefs, attitudes, and delegation varies across application areas, consistent with the idea that perceived stakes, contestability, and prior salience shape how information is processed. This heterogeneity cautions against one-size-fits-all disclosure templates. It also suggests a practical path forward for regulators and firms: if the goal is legitimate uptake, disclosures should be targeted to the dimensions that are most binding in a given domain (e.g., data provenance and privacy in some settings; accountability in others), rather than relying on generic “how it works” language.

Taken together, the paper offers an empirically grounded, Europe-relevant perspective on the economics of algorithmic legitimacy. Our central contribution is to evaluate a disclosure intervention that is (i) lightweight enough to be scalable and legally realistic, (ii) comparable across a wide range of economically important ADM domains, and (iii) measured on outcomes that map directly to adoption and delegation decisions. This combination is what makes the evidence particularly useful for European scientific audiences and policy debates: it bridges legal requirements (disclosure and transparency) and economic mechanisms (belief updating, attitude formation, and delegation choices), and it does so in the population and institutional context where many of these rules are being implemented.

Several limitations point to clear directions for future research. First, our outcomes are stated preferences in a survey setting; field evidence on revealed adoption and realized welfare remains essential. Second, we study one standardized form of explanation; richer disclosures (or interactive explanations) may shift the transparency margin differently, but they may also impose cognitive costs and create new forms of persuasion or overreliance. Third, disclosures are only one component of governance: future work should examine how explanation mandates interact with auditing, contestability rights, and liability regimes, and whether these

bundles differentially affect trust, compliance, and inequality. These extensions are not only policy-relevant; they are also fundamental to understanding when algorithmic systems function as productivity-enhancing complements and when they become contested substitutes.

Our results show that explanations reliably shift beliefs, improve several key evaluative attitudes, and modestly increase willingness to rely on algorithms mainly as decision support. For European policymakers concerned with the legitimacy of algorithmic decision-making, this suggests that well-designed disclosure requirements can be a low-cost complement to stronger institutional safeguards, helping align adoption with informed acceptance rather than blind trust or blanket rejection.

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References

- Adadi, A., & Berrada, M. (2018). Peeking inside the black-box: a survey on explainable artificial intelligence (xai). *IEEE Access*, *6*, 52138–52160.
- Anjomshoae, S., Najjar, A., Calvaresi, D., & Främling, K. (2019). Explainable agents and robots: Results from a systematic literature review. In *18th international conference on autonomous agents and multiagent systems (aamas 2019), montreal, canada, may 13–17, 2019* (pp. 1078–1088).
- Arrieta, A. B., Díaz-Rodríguez, N., Del Ser, J., Bennetot, A., Tabik, S., Barbado, A., ... et al. (2020). Explainable artificial intelligence (xai): Concepts, taxonomies, opportunities and challenges toward responsible ai. *Information Fusion*, *58*, 82–115.
- Aysolmaz, B., Müller, R., & Meacham, D. (2023). The public perceptions of algorithmic decision-making systems: Results from a large-scale survey. *Telematics and Informatics*, *79*, 101954.
- Bansal, G., Zahedi, F. & Gefen, D. (2015). The role of privacy assurance mechanisms in building trust and the moderating role of privacy concern. *European Journal of Information Systems*, *24*(6), 624–644.
- Baron, R. M., & Kenny, D. A. (1986). The moderator–mediator variable distinction in social psychological research: Conceptual, strategic, and statistical considerations. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, *51*(6), 1173–1182. doi: 10.1037/0022-3514.51.6.1173
- Bauer, D. J., Preacher, K. J., & Gil, K. M. (2006). Conceptualizing and testing random indirect effects and moderated mediation in multilevel models: New procedures and recommendations. *Psychological Methods*, *11*(2), 142–163. doi: 10.1037/1082-989X.11.2.142

- Beaudouin, V., Bloch, I., Bounie, D., Cléménçon, S., d’Alché Buc, F., Eagan, J., ... Parekh, J. (2020). Flexible and context-specific ai explainability: a multidisciplinary approach. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2003.07703*.
- Beshears, J., & et al. (2020). Nudging: Progress to date and future directions. *Behavioural Public Policy*.
- Cai, C. J., Jongejan, J., & Holbrook, J. (2019). The effects of example-based explanations in a machine learning interface. In *Proceedings of the 24th international conference on intelligent user interfaces* (pp. 258–262).
- Castelvecchi, D. (2016). Can we open the black box of ai? *Nature*, 538(7623), 20–23.
- Cheng, H.-F., Wang, R., Zhang, Z., O’connell, F., Gray, T., Harper, F. M., & Zhu, H. (2019). Explaining decision-making algorithms through ui: Strategies to help non-expert stakeholders. In *Proceedings of the 2019 chi conference on human factors in computing systems* (pp. 1–12).
- Cohen, S. B., Dror, G., & Ruppín, E. (2005). Feature selection based on the shapley value. In *Proceedings of ijcai* (pp. 1–6).
- Cohodes, S. R. (2022). *When do informational interventions work? experimental evidence from new york city high school choice* (Tech. Rep. No. 29690). NBER.
- Covert, I., Lundberg, S., & Lee, S.-I. (2021). Explaining by removing: A unified framework for model explanation. *Journal of Machine Learning Research*, 22(209), 1–90.
- Cramer, H., Evers, V., Ramlal, S., Van Someren, M., Rutledge, L., Stash, N., ... Wielinga, B. (2008). The effects of transparency on trust in and acceptance of a content-based art recommender. *User Modeling and User-adapted interaction*, 18(5), 455–496.
- Davis, F. D. (1989). Perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, and user acceptance of information technology. *MIS Quarterly*, 13(3), 319–340.
- Dietvorst, B. J., Simmons, J. P., & Massey, C. (2015). Algorithm aversion: people erroneously avoid algorithms after seeing them err. *Journal of experimental psychology: General*, 144(1), 114.
- Dietvorst, B. J., Simmons, J. P., & Massey, C. (2018). Overcoming algorithm aversion: People will use imperfect algorithms if they can (even slightly) modify them. *Management science*, 64(3), 1155–1170.
- Eslami, M., Krishna Kumaran, S. R., Sandvig, C., & Karahalios, K. (2018). Communicating algorithmic process in online behavioral advertising. In *Proceedings of the 2018 chi conference on human factors in computing systems* (pp. 1–13).
- Gefen, D., Karahanna, E., & Straub, D. W. (2003). Trust and tam in online shopping: An integrated model. *MIS Quarterly*, 51–90.
- Gennaioli, N., Shleifer, A., & Vishny, R. (2015). Money doctors. *The Journal of Finance*, 70(1), 91–114.
- Gur, N., & Bjørnskov, C. (2017). Trust and delegation: Theory and evidence. *Journal of Comparative Economics*, 45(3), 644–657.
- Herlocker, J. L., Konstan, J. A., & Riedl, J. (2000). Explaining collaborative filtering recommendations. In *Proceedings of the 2000 acm conference on computer-supported cooperative work* (pp. 241–250).

- Holzmeister, F., Holmén, M., Kirchler, M., Stefan, M., & Wengström, E. (2023). Delegation decisions in finance. *Management Science*, *69*(8), 4828–4844.
- Huberman, G. (2001). Familiarity breeds investment. *The Review of Financial Studies*, *14*(3), 659–680. doi: 10.1093/rfs/14.3.659
- Hyman, J. M. (2020). Can light-touch college-going interventions make a difference? evidence from a statewide experiment in michigan. *Journal of Policy Analysis and Management*, *39*(1), 159–190. doi: 10.1002/pam.22155
- Imai, K., Keele, L., & Tingley, D. (2010). A general approach to causal mediation analysis. *Psychological Methods*, *15*(4), 309–334. doi: 10.1037/a0020761
- Jian, J.-Y., Bisantz, A. M., & Drury, C. G. (2000). Foundations for an empirically determined scale of trust in automated systems. *International Journal of Cognitive Ergonomics*, *4*(1), 53–71.
- Kacianka, S., & Pretschner, A. (2021). Designing accountable systems. In *Proceedings of the 2021 acm conference on fairness, accountability, and transparency* (pp. 424–437).
- Kawaguchi, K. (2021). When will workers follow an algorithm? a field experiment with a retail business. *Management Science*, *67*(3), 1670–1695.
- Lee, M. K. (2018). Understanding perception of algorithmic decisions: Fairness, trust, and emotion in response to algorithmic management. *Big data & Society*, *5*(1), 2053951718756684.
- List, J. A. (2022). *The voltage effect: How to make good ideas great and great ideas scale*. Crown Currency.
- List, J. A. (2023). The voltage effect. *Revue Économique*, *74*(5), 673–680.
- Lundberg, S. M., & Lee, S.-I. (2017). A unified approach to interpreting model predictions. *Advances in neural information processing systems*, *30*.
- Martijn, M., Conati, C., & Verbert, K. (2022). “knowing me, knowing you”: personalized explanations for a music recommender system. *User Modeling and User-Adapted Interaction*, *32*(1-2), 215–252.
- Nunes, I., & Jannach, D. (2017). A systematic review and taxonomy of explanations in decision support and recommender systems. *User Modeling and User-Adapted Interaction*, *27*, 393–444.
- Preece, A., Harborne, D., Braines, D., Tomsett, R., & Chakraborty, S. (2018). Stakeholders in explainable ai. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1810.00184*.
- Rader, E., Cotter, K., & Cho, J. (2018). Explanations as mechanisms for supporting algorithmic transparency. In *Proceedings of the 2018 chi conference on human factors in computing systems* (pp. 1–13).
- Ribeiro, M. T., Singh, S., & Guestrin, C. (2016). “why should i trust you?”: Explaining the predictions of any classifier. In *Proceedings of the 22nd acm sigkdd international conference on knowledge discovery and data mining* (pp. 1135–1144). ACM. doi: 10.1145/2939672.2939778
- Riedl, M. O. (2019). Human-centered artificial intelligence and machine learning. *Human Behavior and Emerging Technologies*, *1*(1), 33–36.
- Shin, D. (2021). The effects of explainability and causability on perception, trust, and acceptance: Implications for explainable ai. *International Journal of Human-Computer Studies*, *146*, 102551.

- Speith, T. (2022). A review of taxonomies of explainable artificial intelligence (xai) methods. In *Proceedings of the 2022 acm conference on fairness, accountability, and transparency* (pp. 2239–2250).
- Sutanto, J., Palme, E., Tan, C.-H., & Phang, C. W. (2013). Addressing the personalization-privacy paradox: An empirical assessment from a field experiment on smartphone users. *MIS Quarterly*, 1141–1164.
- Thaler, R. H., & Sunstein, C. R. (2008). *Nudge: Improving decisions about health, wealth, and happiness*. New Haven, CT: Yale University Press.
- Venkatesh, V., Morris, M. G., Davis, G. B., & Davis, F. D. (2003). User acceptance of information technology: Toward a unified view. *MIS Quarterly*, 27(3), 425–478.
- Wang, W., & Benbasat, I. (2016). Empirical assessment of alternative designs for enhancing different types of trusting beliefs in online recommendation agents. *Journal of Management Information Systems*, 33(3), 744–775.
- Weitz, K., Schiller, D., Schlagowski, R., Huber, T., & André, E. (2021). Let me explain!: exploring the potential of virtual agents in explainable ai interaction design. *Journal on Multimodal User Interfaces*, 15(2), 87–98.
- Wieringa, M. (2020). What to account for when accounting for algorithms: a systematic literature review on algorithmic accountability. In *Proceedings of the 2020 conference on fairness, accountability, and transparency* (pp. 1–18).
- Wright, S. (1921). Correlation and causation. *Journal of Agricultural Research*, 20(7), 557–585.

Appendix

A Survey design appendices

A.1 Items

Table 7: Initial Beliefs Items

Construct	No.	Measurement item	Ref.
Self-Reported Knowledge	K1	I have heard or read about the use of these types of systems that make automated decisions or suggestions. ^a	Aysolmaz et al. (2023)
	K2	I am familiar with these types of systems that make automated decisions or suggestions. ^a	
Perceived exposure	EXP1	I believe I am exposed to these types of systems. ^b	
Self-Reported Use	U1	I believe I use these types of systems. ^b	

^a Response options: Strongly disagree; Disagree; Somewhat disagree; Neutral; Somewhat agree; Agree; Strongly disagree.

^b Response options: Never; Once a decade; Once a year; Once a month; Weekly; Daily; Multiple times in the day.

Table 8: Attitude and Willingness to Delegate Items

Construct	No.	Measurement item	Ref.
Transparency Concerns	TC1	I am concerned that it would not be exactly clear how decisions or suggestions are produced by this system. ^a	Sutanto et al. (2013); Wang and Benbasat (2016)
	TC2	It would bother me if this system does not provide a sufficient explanation about how certain decisions are taken or suggestions are given to me. ^a	–
Perceived Fairness	PF1	I believe that this system in general would treat me fairly when making decisions and suggestions. ^a	Lee (2018)
	PF2	I think that this system would be objective in making decisions or suggestions for me. ^a	–
Perceived Accountability	PA1	If I have any problem with the decisions or suggestions of this system, I believe that the organization providing the system would take necessary measures. ^a	Kacianka and Pretschner (2021); Wieringa (2020)
	PA2	I think that if this system causes harm and nuisance for me then this would be compensated by the organization providing the system. ^a	–
Perceived Usefulness	PU1	I think that I am better off with the decisions and suggestions made by the system. ^a	Gefen et al. (2003)
	PU2	I feel that using this system would make my life more efficient by taking decisions or providing suggestions for me. ^a	–
Privacy Concern	PC1	I am concerned about the use of my personal information by this system. ^a	Bansal et al. (2015)
	PC2	I believe that the privacy of my personal data would be assured while using this system. ^a	–
Perceived Trust	Tr1	I trust that this system would provide high-quality decisions about me. ^a	Jian et al. (2000); Lee (2018)
	Tr2	I believe that this system would not intentionally harm me. ^a	–
Willingness to delegate	WTD1	I would be willing to let this system help/assist me. ^a	Gefen et al. (2003)
	WTD2	I would be willing to delegate my decision rights to this system. / I am willing to let this system make decisions for me. ^a	

^a Response options: Strongly disagree; Disagree; Somewhat disagree; Neutral; Somewhat agree; Agree; Strongly agree.

A.2 Definitions and Explanations

Table 9: System types with definitions and explanations

Type	Definition	Explanation
Credit Scoring Algorithms	A credit scoring algorithm is a tool banks and lenders use to quickly evaluate how likely someone is to repay a loan. It assigns a numeric score indicating creditworthiness based on the person's financial history.	A credit scoring algorithm evaluates an individual's financial history, including debt repayment, credit usage, loan history, and length of credit accounts. Each factor is assigned a numerical value based on its importance in predicting repayment behavior. These values are combined, using weighted calculations, to generate a single numerical score. The algorithm applies statistical methods to ensure the score accurately reflects financial reliability. Finally, this numeric score summarizes the individual's overall creditworthiness.
Online Advertising Algorithms	An online advertising algorithm is a digital system that decides which ads users see on websites or social media platforms. It selects ads based on user interests and behaviors to make advertisements relevant.	An online advertising algorithm tracks user behaviors, such as website visits, clicks, searches, and demographic details. It builds detailed user profiles by analyzing patterns from this collected data. Based on these profiles, the algorithm selects ads that closely align with user interests or predicted preferences. It determines the optimal placement and timing for displaying each advertisement across websites or applications. The algorithm continuously learns and adjusts its ad selections by monitoring user responses and interactions.

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Type	Definition	Explanation
Algorithmic Trading	Algorithmic trading is an automated way of buying and selling financial assets like stocks using computer programs. These programs execute trades quickly based on predefined rules to maximize profit or manage risk.	Algorithmic trading uses automated computer programs that monitor real-time market data, such as price movements, volume, and trends. These programs operate based on predefined rules and trading strategies programmed into the system. When market conditions match these programmed criteria, the algorithms automatically execute buy or sell orders. Trades are performed rapidly, often within milliseconds, without human input. The algorithm continually analyzes market data to adjust or close positions according to its instructions.
Robo-Advisors	A robo-advisor is an automated online service that manages investments and financial planning using computer algorithms. It provides affordable, personalized investment advice without human intervention.	A robo-advisor gathers basic information about a user's financial situation and investment goals, and then applies automated algorithms to analyze this data. It uses these algorithms to select and manage investments, typically assembling them into diversified portfolios. The system continuously monitors market conditions and automatically adjusts the investments as necessary. It regularly provides updates and reports to inform users of their investment progress.
Insurance Premium Calculation Algorithms	An insurance premium calculation algorithm determines how much a person should pay for insurance coverage. It sets premiums based on factors that predict the likelihood and cost of potential claims.	An insurance premium calculation algorithm analyzes data such as age, health history, driving behavior, or property characteristics. It assigns numerical risk values to these factors based on their likelihood of causing future claims. Each factor is weighted according to its significance in influencing potential claim costs. The algorithm combines these weighted factors to compute a total risk score. This score directly translates into the premium amount charged to the policyholder.

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Type	Definition	Explanation
Healthcare Diagnosis Algorithms for Experts	Healthcare diagnosis algorithms are computational tools designed to support medical professionals by systematically interpreting clinical data. They aid in identifying diseases or conditions by analyzing symptoms, test results, and patient history.	Healthcare diagnosis algorithms process patient data, including symptoms, medical history, lab results, and imaging. They compare this data against extensive medical databases and clinical guidelines. Algorithms identify patterns by matching patient information with known diagnostic criteria. Through statistical or machine learning methods, they calculate the likelihood of different medical conditions. The algorithm then provides clinicians with potential diagnoses ranked by probability.
Medical Assistant or Medical Chatbot	A medical assistant or medical chatbot is an automated digital tool designed to interact with users about health-related questions or concerns. It provides instant guidance, symptom assessment, or basic medical information through conversational interactions.	A medical assistant or chatbot receives user input in the form of text or voice-based questions. It uses algorithms to interpret and understand these inputs through natural language processing. The chatbot matches the interpreted query to relevant medical information stored in its database. It generates responses based on predefined guidelines or machine learning models trained on clinical data. Finally, it communicates its response back to the user in a conversational format.
Job Application Screening Algorithms	A job application screening algorithm is an automated tool employers use to quickly evaluate job applicants. It filters and ranks candidates based on their resumes, experience, skills, and qualifications.	A job application screening algorithm scans resumes and applications submitted by candidates. It identifies and extracts keywords, qualifications, experience, education, and skills mentioned within these documents. The algorithm compares extracted information against predefined criteria from the job description. Applicants are ranked or scored based on how closely their profiles match the required criteria. Finally, it generates a shortlist of candidates who best align with the job requirements.

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Type	Definition	Explanation
Predictive Policing Algorithms	A predictive policing algorithm is a computational tool used by law enforcement to anticipate where or when crimes might occur. It analyzes historical crime data to guide policing efforts proactively.	A predictive policing algorithm analyzes historical crime data, such as locations, times, types, and frequency of past incidents. It identifies patterns or trends within this data using statistical or machine-learning techniques. The algorithm then calculates probabilities to estimate where and when crimes might occur next. It generates maps or reports highlighting areas at higher risk of future crimes. These predictions guide police deployments and patrol strategies.
Recommendation Algorithms	A recommendation algorithm is an automated system that suggests items, content, or services to users based on their preferences or behaviors. It provides personalized recommendations, such as movies, products, or articles, to enhance user experience.	A recommendation algorithm tracks user interactions, such as clicks, views, ratings, or purchases. It analyzes this data to identify patterns and similarities among users or items. The algorithm applies statistical or machine learning methods to predict user preferences. Based on these predictions, it selects and ranks items that closely match individual user profiles. Finally, the algorithm presents personalized suggestions directly to the user interface.
Search Engine Algorithms	A search engine algorithm is a computerized method that finds and ranks relevant web pages in response to a user's query. It determines which results best match the search terms entered.	A search engine algorithm scans billions of web pages, collecting and indexing content such as text, images, and links. It analyzes user-entered keywords or phrases to determine their intent. The algorithm then compares these keywords against its indexed pages to find relevant matches. It ranks results based on factors like keyword relevance, page quality, popularity, and user engagement. Finally, the algorithm displays a list of web pages organized by their ranking.

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Type	Definition	Explanation
Social Media Algorithms	A social media algorithm is an automated system that selects and organizes content displayed on users' feeds. It determines which posts users see first based on their interests and behaviors.	A social media algorithm monitors user interactions such as likes, shares, comments, and views. It analyzes this data to build personalized profiles reflecting individual interests and behaviors. The algorithm ranks content by assessing its relevance to these user profiles. It prioritizes and arranges posts, stories, or videos accordingly within user feeds. The content displayed continuously updates based on ongoing user interactions.

Prompt (Model: GPT-4.5). Definition: Give a definition of a [System Type] in two lines, without tackling its inner workings, for a non-stakeholder. Explanation: Provide an explanation of [System Type]'s inner workings in five lines for a non-stakeholder. Only limit yourself to how it works and not why it is used.

A.3 Biased explanations that have not been used

Table 10: Biased explanations that have not been used

Type	Definition	Explanation
Credit Scoring Algorithms	A credit scoring algorithm is a predictive model that evaluates an individual's creditworthiness. It generates a numerical score used by lenders to make credit decisions.	A credit scoring algorithm collects financial data such as payment history, outstanding debt, credit utilization, and length of credit history. It assigns weights to these factors based on their predictive power in determining credit risk. The algorithm processes this data using statistical models or machine learning techniques to generate a credit score. Higher scores indicate lower credit risk, while lower scores suggest a higher likelihood of default. Lenders use these scores to assess loan eligibility, interest rates, and credit limits.

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Type	Definition	Explanation
Online Advertising Algorithms	An online advertising algorithm is a system that automatically selects and delivers ads to users based on relevant data. It optimizes ad placement to maximize engagement, conversions, or revenue for advertisers and platforms.	An online advertising algorithm collects user data such as browsing behavior, demographics, and interests. It analyzes this data using machine learning or rule-based models to predict which ads are most relevant to each user. The algorithm then selects and ranks ads in real time through auctions or bidding systems, balancing factors like advertiser bids and user engagement likelihood. It continuously optimizes ad performance by adjusting targeting parameters based on feedback and interaction data. This process ensures higher ad relevance, maximizing clicks, conversions, and revenue for advertisers and platforms.
Algorithmic Trading	Algorithmic trading is the automated execution of financial market trades using preprogrammed rules and mathematical models. It enables rapid, data-driven decision-making to optimize trading strategies and efficiency.	Algorithmic trading uses computer programs to analyze market data, identify patterns, and execute trades based on predefined strategies. It incorporates factors like price movements, volume, and technical indicators to make rapid decisions. The algorithm can place, modify, or cancel orders in milliseconds, often leveraging high-frequency trading techniques. Risk management rules are embedded to control exposure, minimize losses, and optimize profits. Continuous backtesting and machine learning help refine strategies for better market performance.

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Type	Definition	Explanation
Robo-Advisors	A robo-advisor is an automated investment platform that provides financial advice and portfolio management with minimal human intervention. It uses algorithms to tailor investment strategies based on user preferences and risk tolerance.	Robo-advisors collect user data, including financial goals, risk tolerance, and investment preferences, through digital questionnaires. They use algorithms to analyze this data and construct a diversified portfolio based on modern portfolio theory or other optimization techniques. The system automatically rebalances the portfolio by adjusting asset allocations in response to market fluctuations. Tax-loss harvesting and other strategies are applied to optimize returns and minimize tax liabilities. Continuous monitoring and machine learning improvements enhance investment strategies over time to align with user objectives.
Insurance Premium Calculation Algorithms	An insurance premium calculation algorithm is a system that determines the cost of an insurance policy based on risk factors. It analyzes data to calculate a fair and competitive premium for policyholders.	An insurance premium calculation algorithm collects and analyzes data on factors like age, health, driving history, or property details, depending on the type of insurance. It assigns risk scores based on statistical models, actuarial tables, or machine learning techniques. The algorithm calculates the probability of a claim and adjusts the premium accordingly to cover potential losses while ensuring profitability. Discounts or surcharges may be applied based on additional risk variables, behavior, or policyholder history. The system continuously refines its calculations using updated data and predictive modeling to improve accuracy and competitiveness.

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Type	Definition	Explanation
Healthcare Diagnosis Algorithms for Experts	A healthcare diagnosis algorithm for experts is a system that assists medical professionals in identifying diseases based on patient data. It analyzes symptoms, medical history, and test results to provide diagnostic insights and recommendations.	A healthcare diagnosis algorithm processes patient data, including symptoms, medical history, imaging, and lab results. It uses machine learning models, statistical analysis, or rule-based systems to identify patterns linked to specific diseases. The algorithm compares patient data against vast medical databases to suggest possible diagnoses and their probabilities. It continuously learns from new cases, improving accuracy and adapting to emerging medical trends. Doctors use the algorithm's insights to support decision-making, ensuring faster and more precise diagnoses while maintaining human oversight.
Medical Assistant or Medical Chatbot	A medical assistant or medical chatbot is an AI-powered system that provides health-related information, symptom assessment, and guidance. It interacts with users to answer medical queries, suggest possible conditions, and recommend next steps.	A medical assistant or chatbot processes user input, such as symptoms and medical questions, using natural language processing (NLP) to understand intent. It accesses medical databases, guidelines, and machine learning models to analyze symptoms and provide possible conditions or advice. The chatbot applies decision trees or AI-driven algorithms to assess risk levels and recommend next steps, such as self-care or seeking professional help. It continuously improves through user interactions, feedback, and updates to medical knowledge. While it offers preliminary guidance, it does not replace professional medical advice and often suggests consulting a healthcare provider when necessary.

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Type	Definition	Explanation
Job Application Screening Algorithms	A job application screening algorithm is an automated system that evaluates and filters job candidates based on predefined criteria. It analyzes resumes and applications to identify the most suitable candidates for a position.	A job application screening algorithm collects and processes resumes, cover letters, and application data using natural language processing (NLP) and keyword matching. It compares candidate qualifications, skills, and experience against job requirements set by recruiters. Machine learning models or rule-based systems rank applicants based on relevance, eliminating those who do not meet essential criteria. Some algorithms assess additional factors like work history patterns, employment gaps, or predictive hiring success. The system continuously refines its filtering process based on recruiter feedback and hiring outcomes to improve accuracy over time.
Predictive Policing Algorithms	A predictive policing algorithm is a data-driven system that forecasts potential criminal activity based on historical crime data and patterns. It helps law enforcement allocate resources and prevent crimes before they occur.	A predictive policing algorithm analyzes historical crime data, including locations, times, and types of offenses, to identify patterns and trends. It applies statistical models or machine learning techniques to forecast areas or individuals at higher risk of criminal activity. Law enforcement agencies use these predictions to allocate patrols, monitor hotspots, or assess potential threats. The algorithm continuously updates its predictions using new crime reports and real-time data to improve accuracy. Ethical concerns, such as bias in data and potential profiling, require careful oversight and evaluation of the algorithm's impact.

Continued on next page

Type	Definition	Explanation
Recommendation Algorithms	A recommendation algorithm is a system that suggests relevant content, products, or services to users based on their preferences and behavior. It personalizes recommendations to enhance user experience and engagement.	A recommendation algorithm collects user data, such as browsing history, interactions, and preferences, to understand individual behavior. It applies techniques like collaborative filtering, content-based filtering, or hybrid models to identify patterns and similarities between users or items. The algorithm ranks and suggests relevant content, products, or services based on past interactions and predictive analysis. Continuous learning from user feedback and engagement helps refine recommendations over time. This process enhances personalization, improving user experience and driving engagement or sales.
Search Engine Algorithms	A search engine algorithm is a system that retrieves and ranks web pages based on user queries. It analyzes and organizes information to deliver the most relevant and useful search results.	A search engine algorithm crawls and indexes web pages by scanning their content, structure, and metadata. It processes user queries using natural language processing (NLP) and keyword matching to understand intent. The algorithm ranks results based on relevance, authority, and user experience factors like backlinks, content quality, and page speed. Machine learning and user behavior data continuously refine rankings to improve accuracy. Regular updates adjust ranking criteria to combat spam, ensure fairness, and enhance search result quality.

Continued on next page

Type	Definition	Explanation
Social Media Algorithms	A social media algorithm is a system that curates and prioritizes content for users based on their interactions and preferences. It determines what appears in feeds to enhance engagement and user experience.	A social media algorithm collects user data, including likes, shares, comments, and watch time, to understand engagement patterns. It ranks and prioritizes content using machine learning models that assess relevance, recency, and user interests. The algorithm adjusts recommendations based on factors like trending topics, relationships, and content type to maximize user interaction. Continuous feedback loops refine content delivery, ensuring personalization and optimizing engagement over time. Platforms frequently update their algorithms to balance user experience, advertiser goals, and content diversity.

Prompt (Model: GPT-4o mini). Definition: Define what a [System Type] is in two lines without explaining the inner workings.

Explanation: Explain the inner workings of a [System Type] in five lines.

B Additional Results

B.1 Additional Figures

B.1.1 Beliefs Items

Figure 8: Self-Reported Knowledge

Figure 9: Self-Reported Familiarity

Figure 10: Perceived Exposure

Figure 11: Self-Reported Use

B.1.2 Attitudes Items

Figure 12: Transparency Concerns 1

Figure 13: Transparency Concerns 2

(a) Baseline

(b) Treated

Figure 14: Perceived Fairness 1

(a) Baseline

(b) Treated

Figure 15: Perceived Fairness 2

Figure 16: Perceived Accountability 1

Figure 17: Perceived Accountability 2

(a) Baseline

(b) Treated

Figure 18: Privacy Concern 1

(a) Baseline

(b) Treated

Figure 19: Privacy Concern 2

(a) Baseline

(b) Treated

Figure 20: Perceived Trust 1

(a) Baseline

(b) Treated

Figure 21: Perceived Trust 2

(a) Baseline

(b) Treated

Figure 22: Perceived Usefulness 1

(a) Baseline

(b) Treated

Figure 23: Perceived Usefulness 2

B.1.3 Willingness to Delegate Items

Figure 24: Willingness to Delegate (Weak Delegation, WTD1)

Figure 25: Willingness to Delegate (Strong Delegation, WTD2)

B.1.4 Indices Items

Figure 26: Index (Sum)

Figure 27: Index (PCA)

B.2 Descriptive Statistics

B.2.1 Sample

Table 11: Sample characteristics by country

	France	Germany	Italy
N	1000	1003	1004
Age			
Mean (SD)	48.09 (17.03)	48.29 (16.67)	47.39 (15.10)
Range [min, max]	[18, 83]	[18, 88]	[18, 86]
Education			
No formal education	12 (1.2%)	8 (0.8%)	2 (0.2%)
Primary education	21 (2.1%)	30 (3.0%)	37 (3.7%)
Secondary education (e.g., high school)	239 (23.9%)	163 (16.3%)	353 (35.2%)
Vocational or technical training	189 (18.9%)	307 (30.6%)	152 (15.1%)
Associate degree or equivalent	197 (19.7%)	177 (17.6%)	86 (8.6%)
Bachelor's degree	158 (15.8%)	126 (12.6%)	119 (11.9%)
Master's degree	141 (14.1%)	156 (15.6%)	192 (19.1%)
Doctorate or equivalent	35 (3.5%)	29 (2.9%)	60 (6.0%)
Prefer not to say	8 (0.8%)	7 (0.7%)	3 (0.3%)
Employment			
Employed full-time	499 (49.9%)	431 (43.0%)	461 (45.9%)
Employed part-time	72 (7.2%)	139 (13.9%)	80 (8.0%)
Self-employed	34 (3.4%)	58 (5.8%)	106 (10.6%)
Unemployed (looking for work)	40 (4.0%)	31 (3.1%)	68 (6.8%)
Unemployed (not looking for work)	9 (0.9%)	4 (0.4%)	5 (0.5%)
Retired	252 (25.2%)	234 (23.3%)	121 (12.1%)
Student	42 (4.2%)	29 (2.9%)	66 (6.6%)
Homemaker	34 (3.4%)	52 (5.2%)	87 (8.7%)
Unable to work	15 (1.5%)	22 (2.2%)	5 (0.5%)
Prefer not to say	3 (0.3%)	3 (0.3%)	5 (0.5%)

Table 11: Sample characteristics by country (*continued*)

	France	Germany	Italy
Gender			
Male	479 (47.9%)	482 (48.1%)	479 (47.7%)
Female	519 (51.9%)	514 (51.2%)	522 (52.0%)
Non-binary / Third gender	2 (0.2%)	3 (0.3%)	NA
Prefer to self-describe	NA	3 (0.3%)	NA
Prefer not to say	NA	1 (0.1%)	3 (0.3%)
Income			
No income	17 (1.7%)	27 (2.7%)	77 (7.7%)
Under \$10,000	103 (10.3%)	84 (8.4%)	91 (9.1%)
\$10,000–\$24,999	301 (30.1%)	225 (22.4%)	259 (25.8%)
\$25,000–\$39,999	281 (28.1%)	227 (22.6%)	281 (28.0%)
\$40,000–\$59,999	165 (16.5%)	177 (17.6%)	142 (14.1%)
\$60,000–\$79,999	56 (5.6%)	113 (11.3%)	52 (5.2%)
\$80,000–\$99,999	21 (2.1%)	53 (5.3%)	23 (2.3%)
\$100,000 or more	16 (1.6%)	48 (4.8%)	20 (2.0%)
Prefer not to say	40 (4.0%)	49 (4.9%)	59 (5.9%)
Marital Status			
Single	274 (27.4%)	103 (10.3%)	274 (27.3%)
Never married	8 (0.8%)	192 (19.1%)	21 (2.1%)
Married or in a registered partnership	475 (47.5%)	464 (46.3%)	447 (44.5%)
Living with partner (cohabiting)	125 (12.5%)	116 (11.6%)	156 (15.5%)
Separated; Divorced	93 (9.3%)	92 (9.2%)	77 (7.7%)
Widowed	24 (2.4%)	34 (3.4%)	22 (2.2%)
Prefer not to say	1 (0.1%)	2 (0.2%)	7 (0.7%)

B.2.2 Beliefs Items

System	Self-Reported Knowledge M / SD	Self-Reported Familiarity M / SD	Perceived Exposure M / SD	Self-Reported Use M / SD
Algorithmic Trading	3.72 (1.87)	3.32 (1.83)	2.61 (1.85)	2.43 (1.83)
Credit Scoring	4.01 (1.82)	3.60 (1.77)	2.83 (1.84)	2.52 (1.79)
Healthcare Diagnosis	4.07 (1.76)	3.53 (1.75)	2.77 (1.82)	2.52 (1.82)
Insurance Premium	4.04 (1.69)	3.79 (1.71)	3.10 (1.77)	2.78 (1.82)
Job Application	3.90 (1.81)	3.55 (1.81)	2.74 (1.90)	2.55 (1.90)
Medical Chatbot	4.11 (1.74)	3.53 (1.80)	2.64 (1.81)	2.56 (1.82)
Online Advertising	4.31 (1.80)	4.03 (1.83)	4.18 (2.14)	3.43 (2.16)
Predictive Policing	3.43 (1.85)	3.07 (1.77)	2.36 (1.83)	2.16 (1.76)
Recommendation	4.35 (1.75)	4.12 (1.80)	3.95 (2.12)	3.55 (2.12)
Robo-Advisors	3.85 (1.80)	3.56 (1.77)	2.87 (1.91)	2.58 (1.89)
Search Engine	4.52 (1.65)	4.46 (1.64)	4.48 (1.98)	4.31 (2.03)
Social Media	4.55 (1.66)	4.33 (1.67)	4.40 (1.99)	4.13 (2.06)
Mean	4.07 (1.77)	3.74 (1.76)	3.24 (1.91)	2.96 (1.92)

Table 12: Mean belief score per system and overall belief score, Baseline

System	Self-Reported Knowledge M / SD	Self-Reported Familiarity M / SD	Perceived Exposure M / SD	Self-Reported Use M / SD
Algorithmic Trading	4.00 (1.80)	3.55 (1.73)	2.92 (2.08)	2.61 (1.99)
Credit Scoring	3.95 (1.70)	3.69 (1.69)	2.86 (1.86)	2.64 (1.84)
Healthcare Diagnosis	4.36 (1.57)	4.17 (1.59)	3.03 (1.82)	3.03 (1.97)
Insurance Premium	3.83 (1.79)	3.62 (1.75)	2.80 (1.78)	2.56 (1.83)
Job Application	3.93 (1.82)	3.43 (1.80)	2.53 (1.89)	2.37 (1.90)
Medical Chatbot	4.32 (1.59)	3.81 (1.66)	2.97 (1.87)	2.83 (1.87)
Online Advertising	4.66 (1.54)	4.44 (1.53)	4.95 (1.88)	4.38 (2.04)
Predictive Policing	3.64 (1.84)	3.17 (1.81)	2.37 (1.81)	2.16 (1.77)
Recommendation	4.74 (1.53)	4.44 (1.56)	4.43 (1.90)	4.13 (1.97)
Robo-Advisors	3.80 (1.88)	3.33 (1.83)	2.48 (1.84)	2.39 (1.86)
Search Engine	4.79 (1.60)	4.59 (1.61)	4.75 (1.98)	4.63 (2.02)
Social Media	4.59 (1.68)	4.35 (1.69)	4.46 (2.17)	4.10 (2.22)
Mean	4.22 (1.69)	3.88 (1.69)	3.38 (1.91)	3.15 (1.94)

Table 13: Mean belief score per system and overall belief score, Treated

B.2.3 Attitudes Items

Table 14: Mean attitude score per system and overall attitude score, Baseline (Panel A: Transparency, Fairness, Accountability)

System	TC1	TC2	PF1	PF2	PA1	PA2
	M / SD					
Algorithmic	3.47	3.37	4.09	4.09	4.00	3.84
Trading	(1.48)	(1.49)	(1.49)	(1.49)	(1.47)	(1.57)
Credit	3.37	3.19	4.08	4.09	4.00	3.71
Scoring	(1.50)	(1.56)	(1.56)	(1.52)	(1.57)	(1.68)
Healthcare	3.42	3.20	4.37	4.41	4.29	4.03
Diagnosis	(1.43)	(1.42)	(1.46)	(1.44)	(1.47)	(1.55)
Insurance	3.37	3.24	4.38	4.33	4.28	4.03
Premium	(1.38)	(1.43)	(1.41)	(1.41)	(1.41)	(1.55)
Job	3.42	3.27	4.05	4.09	4.04	3.88
Application	(1.49)	(1.49)	(1.52)	(1.51)	(1.51)	(1.61)
Medical	3.50	3.34	4.31	4.25	4.12	3.83
Chatbot	(1.41)	(1.50)	(1.43)	(1.49)	(1.51)	(1.57)
Online	3.44	3.37	3.93	3.86	3.86	3.66
Advertising	(1.51)	(1.53)	(1.51)	(1.58)	(1.59)	(1.66)
Predictive	3.44	3.29	4.15	4.06	4.08	3.90
Policing	(1.51)	(1.51)	(1.51)	(1.52)	(1.50)	(1.54)
Recommendation	3.42	3.32	4.30	4.27	4.13	3.93
	(1.43)	(1.42)	(1.42)	(1.48)	(1.52)	(1.58)
Robo-Advisors	3.35	3.22	4.25	4.23	4.12	3.95
	(1.34)	(1.46)	(1.42)	(1.40)	(1.45)	(1.52)
Search Engine	3.46	3.25	4.45	4.37	4.15	3.92
	(1.36)	(1.33)	(1.36)	(1.37)	(1.38)	(1.48)
Social Media	3.47	3.41	4.11	4.14	3.96	3.94
	(1.44)	(1.49)	(1.48)	(1.52)	(1.52)	(1.73)
Mean	3.43	3.29	4.21	4.18	4.08	3.89
	(1.44)	(1.47)	(1.46)	(1.48)	(1.49)	(1.59)

Table 15: Mean attitude score per system and overall attitude score, Baseline (Panel B: Privacy, Trust, Use)

System	PC1	PC2	PTru1	PTru2	PU1	PU2
	M / SD					
Algorithmic	3.42	4.00	3.98	4.21	3.87	3.97
Trading	(1.51)	(1.55)	(1.53)	(1.47)	(1.53)	(1.54)
Credit	3.35	3.99	4.00	4.19	3.81	3.81
Scoring	(1.53)	(1.57)	(1.62)	(1.43)	(1.59)	(1.64)
Healthcare	3.46	4.27	4.39	4.58	4.23	4.25
Diagnosis	(1.55)	(1.53)	(1.46)	(1.41)	(1.49)	(1.51)
Insurance	3.43	4.25	4.23	4.41	4.15	4.19
Premium	(1.43)	(1.48)	(1.43)	(1.39)	(1.44)	(1.48)
Job	3.48	4.01	3.96	4.27	3.84	3.93
Application	(1.58)	(1.56)	(1.55)	(1.48)	(1.60)	(1.60)
Medical	3.44	4.04	4.15	4.38	4.00	4.05
Chatbot	(1.56)	(1.55)	(1.45)	(1.42)	(1.50)	(1.46)
Online	3.16	3.68	3.78	4.16	3.75	3.77
Advertising	(1.57)	(1.62)	(1.63)	(1.54)	(1.62)	(1.67)
Predictive	3.36	3.99	4.10	4.29	3.96	3.96
Policing	(1.54)	(1.57)	(1.51)	(1.49)	(1.52)	(1.55)
Recommendation	3.29	4.05	4.24	4.45	4.10	4.19
	(1.49)	(1.57)	(1.50)	(1.44)	(1.49)	(1.52)
Robo-Advisors	3.45	4.17	4.19	4.37	4.09	4.19
	(1.47)	(1.47)	(1.44)	(1.43)	(1.47)	(1.48)
Search Engine	3.17	4.17	4.39	4.49	4.30	4.27
	(1.43)	(1.41)	(1.36)	(1.34)	(1.37)	(1.48)
Social Media	3.22	3.99	4.05	4.14	4.03	4.04
	(1.48)	(1.63)	(1.48)	(1.39)	(1.55)	(1.55)
Mean	3.35	4.05	4.12	4.33	4.01	4.05
	(1.51)	(1.54)	(1.50)	(1.44)	(1.51)	(1.54)

Table 16: Mean attitude score per system and overall attitude score, Treated (Panel A: Transparency, Fairness, Accountability)

System	TC1	TC2	PF1	PF2	PA1	PA2
	M / SD					
Algorithmic	3.38	3.28	4.31	4.40	4.18	4.02
Trading	(1.39)	(1.42)	(1.45)	(1.43)	(1.50)	(1.61)
Credit	3.42	3.25	4.26	4.26	4.13	3.95
Scoring	(1.40)	(1.39)	(1.44)	(1.44)	(1.49)	(1.57)
Healthcare	3.56	3.22	4.68	4.78	4.52	4.42
Diagnosis	(1.41)	(1.30)	(1.24)	(1.26)	(1.46)	(1.48)
Insurance	3.39	3.13	4.34	4.30	4.16	4.01
Premium	(1.43)	(1.44)	(1.48)	(1.47)	(1.53)	(1.59)
Job	3.45	3.29	4.18	4.15	3.98	3.82
Application	(1.38)	(1.42)	(1.50)	(1.50)	(1.57)	(1.71)
Medical	3.34	3.16	4.47	4.39	4.32	4.10
Chatbot	(1.39)	(1.38)	(1.43)	(1.45)	(1.48)	(1.57)
Online	3.32	3.25	4.24	4.22	4.16	3.93
Advertising	(1.34)	(1.30)	(1.47)	(1.48)	(1.52)	(1.59)
Predictive	3.67	3.35	4.27	4.30	4.19	3.93
Policing	(1.50)	(1.48)	(1.55)	(1.52)	(1.65)	(1.67)
Recommendation	3.50	3.23	4.42	4.37	4.16	3.91
	(1.40)	(1.34)	(1.41)	(1.48)	(1.51)	(1.65)
Robo-Advisors	3.49	3.32	4.23	4.24	4.07	3.80
	(1.51)	(1.48)	(1.52)	(1.52)	(1.57)	(1.70)
Search Engine	3.49	3.26	4.53	4.50	4.28	4.01
	(1.41)	(1.36)	(1.40)	(1.41)	(1.50)	(1.60)
Social Media	3.38	3.20	4.20	4.16	4.09	3.83
	(1.43)	(1.39)	(1.47)	(1.51)	(1.55)	(1.66)
Mean	3.45	3.25	4.34	4.34	4.19	3.98
	(1.42)	(1.39)	(1.45)	(1.46)	(1.53)	(1.62)

Table 17: Mean attitude score per system and overall attitude score, Treated (Panel B: Privacy, Trust, Use)

System	PC1	PC2	PTru1	PTru2	PU1	PU2
	M / SD					
Algorithmic	3.30	4.25	4.31	4.43	4.14	4.26
Trading	(1.47)	(1.55)	(1.46)	(1.40)	(1.54)	(1.52)
Credit	3.36	4.18	4.26	4.35	4.04	3.99
Scoring	(1.49)	(1.52)	(1.47)	(1.41)	(1.47)	(1.52)
Healthcare	3.56	4.68	4.72	4.89	4.70	4.79
Diagnosis	(1.49)	(1.32)	(1.26)	(1.25)	(1.30)	(1.26)
Insurance	3.33	4.11	4.25	4.43	4.07	4.08
Premium	(1.53)	(1.52)	(1.51)	(1.43)	(1.53)	(1.54)
Job	3.49	4.12	4.10	4.31	3.93	3.95
Application	(1.53)	(1.54)	(1.51)	(1.41)	(1.54)	(1.58)
Medical	3.36	4.24	4.31	4.60	4.09	4.14
Chatbot	(1.52)	(1.54)	(1.49)	(1.37)	(1.52)	(1.57)
Online	3.17	4.08	4.26	4.43	4.04	4.09
Advertising	(1.43)	(1.61)	(1.53)	(1.40)	(1.51)	(1.53)
Predictive	3.58	4.13	4.22	4.48	4.18	4.05
Policing	(1.59)	(1.66)	(1.61)	(1.52)	(1.57)	(1.63)
Recommendation	3.37	4.21	4.32	4.55	4.24	4.30
	(1.53)	(1.54)	(1.51)	(1.44)	(1.47)	(1.55)
Robo-Advisors	3.30	4.06	4.14	4.33	4.06	4.07
	(1.62)	(1.62)	(1.57)	(1.51)	(1.55)	(1.62)
Search Engine	3.33	4.31	4.51	4.65	4.37	4.45
	(1.48)	(1.52)	(1.44)	(1.41)	(1.46)	(1.51)
Social Media	3.18	3.98	4.17	4.39	4.03	4.06
	(1.50)	(1.62)	(1.55)	(1.43)	(1.57)	(1.62)
Mean	3.36	4.19	4.30	4.49	4.16	4.19
	(1.51)	(1.54)	(1.49)	(1.42)	(1.50)	(1.54)

B.2.4 Willingness to Delegate Items

System	Willingness to Delegate (Weak)	Willingness to Delegate (Strong)
	M / SD	M / SD
Algorithmic Trading	3.96 (1.58)	3.64 (1.65)
Credit Scoring	3.95 (1.65)	3.52 (1.73)
Healthcare Diagnosis	4.32 (1.53)	3.85 (1.61)
Insurance Premium	4.27 (1.49)	3.89 (1.57)
Job Application	3.96 (1.62)	3.66 (1.66)
Medical Chatbot	4.18 (1.50)	3.66 (1.67)
Online Advertising	3.76 (1.72)	3.42 (1.74)
Predictive Policing	4.01 (1.58)	3.69 (1.67)
Recommendation	4.17 (1.56)	3.78 (1.66)
Robo-Advisors	4.09 (1.53)	3.79 (1.61)
Search Engine	4.47 (1.42)	3.86 (1.63)
Social Media	4.12 (1.60)	3.72 (1.70)
Mean	4.11 (1.57)	3.71 (1.66)

Table 18: Mean WTD score per system and overall WTD score, Baseline

System	Willingness to Delegate (Weak)	Willingness to Delegate (Strong)
Algorithmic Trading	4.20 (1.55)	3.85 (1.64)
Credit Scoring	4.12 (1.54)	3.74 (1.61)
Healthcare Diagnosis	4.74 (1.33)	4.24 (1.60)
Insurance Premium	4.19 (1.55)	3.80 (1.70)
Job Application	4.09 (1.59)	3.77 (1.68)
Medical Chatbot	4.30 (1.56)	3.79 (1.73)
Online Advertising	4.11 (1.60)	3.75 (1.73)
Predictive Policing	4.29 (1.59)	3.73 (1.71)
Recommendation	4.37 (1.53)	3.75 (1.72)
Robo-Advisors	3.99 (1.70)	3.68 (1.74)
Search Engine	4.59 (1.49)	3.85 (1.68)
Social Media	4.05 (1.63)	3.66 (1.71)
Mean	4.25 (1.55)	3.80 (1.69)

Table 19: Mean WTD score per system and overall WTD score, Treated

B.2.5 Indices Items

System	Index (Sum)	Index (PCA)
	M / SD	M / SD
Algorithmic Trading	66.00 (17.99)	-0.19 (1.03)
Credit Scoring	66.01 (18.59)	-0.17 (1.02)
Healthcare Diagnosis	69.95 (16.86)	0.04 (0.98)
Insurance Premium	70.16 (16.31)	0.04 (0.96)
Job Application	66.61 (18.36)	-0.16 (1.05)
Medical Chatbot	68.10 (16.84)	-0.09 (0.99)
Online Advertising	67.54 (18.60)	-0.15 (1.05)
Predictive Policing	65.30 (17.68)	-0.19 (1.00)
Recommendation	71.62 (17.27)	0.08 (0.98)
Robo-Advisors	68.33 (17.11)	-0.04 (0.98)
Search Engine	74.50 (14.97)	0.22 (0.90)
Social Media	71.77 (16.33)	0.04 (1.00)
Mean	68.82 (17.24)	-0.05 (1.00)

Table 20: Mean index score per system and overall mean index score, Baseline

System	Index (Sum)	Index (PCA)
	M / SD	M / SD
Algorithmic Trading	69.39 (17.91)	0.02 (1.00)
Credit Scoring	68.45 (17.06)	-0.05 (0.96)
Healthcare Diagnosis	76.10 (14.33)	0.33 (0.87)
Insurance Premium	68.40 (17.95)	-0.02 (0.99)
Job Application	66.91 (18.07)	-0.14 (1.02)
Medical Chatbot	70.53 (17.55)	0.08 (0.97)
Online Advertising	73.46 (16.42)	0.16 (0.94)
Predictive Policing	67.72 (18.39)	-0.11 (1.05)
Recommendation	74.45 (17.03)	0.19 (0.97)
Robo-Advisors	66.77 (19.29)	-0.13 (1.04)
Search Engine	76.90 (16.48)	0.32 (0.94)
Social Media	71.87 (18.05)	0.09 (0.99)
Moyenne	70.91 (17.38)	0.06 (0.98)

Table 21: Mean index score per system and overall mean index score, Treated

B.3 Additional Tables

Table 22: WTD1 decomposition by system: Sum indices vs PCA indices

Component	Sum indices	PCA indices
<i>Algorithmic Trading</i>		
Direct (\hat{d})	0.031 (0.033)	0.029 (0.034)
Indirect via beliefs ($\hat{a}\hat{e}$)	0.023*** (0.008)	0.015*** (0.006)
Indirect via attitudes ($\hat{c}\hat{f}$)	0.061* (0.032)	0.059* (0.032)
Indirect via beliefs→attitudes ($\hat{a}\hat{b}\hat{f}$)	0.054*** (0.018)	0.066*** (0.022)
Total	0.169*** (0.054)	0.169*** (0.054)
<i>Credit Scoring</i>		
Direct (\hat{d})	-0.010 (0.040)	0.021 (0.043)
Indirect via beliefs ($\hat{a}\hat{e}$)	0.012 (0.009)	0.007 (0.006)
Indirect via attitudes ($\hat{c}\hat{f}$)	0.064 (0.038)	0.036 (0.036)
Indirect via beliefs→attitudes ($\hat{a}\hat{b}\hat{f}$)	0.024 (0.018)	0.028 (0.021)
Total	0.091 (0.057)	0.091 (0.057)
<i>Healthcare Diagnosis</i>		
Direct (\hat{d})	-0.012 (0.055)	0.039 (0.057)
Indirect via beliefs ($\hat{a}\hat{e}$)	0.018 (0.011)	0.007* (0.005)
Indirect via attitudes ($\hat{c}\hat{f}$)	0.156*** (0.043)	0.094** (0.042)
Indirect via beliefs→attitudes ($\hat{a}\hat{b}\hat{f}$)	0.040 (0.024)	0.063* (0.032)
Total	0.203** (0.074)	0.203** (0.074)
<i>Insurance Premium</i>		
Direct (\hat{d})	0.047 (0.047)	0.000 (0.046)
Indirect via beliefs ($\hat{a}\hat{e}$)	0.015 (0.011)	0.007 (0.006)
Indirect via attitudes ($\hat{c}\hat{f}$)	0.024 (0.039)	0.075* (0.040)
Indirect via beliefs→attitudes ($\hat{a}\hat{b}\hat{f}$)	0.028 (0.020)	0.033 (0.025)
Total	0.115* (0.067)	0.115* (0.067)
<i>Job Application</i>		
Direct (\hat{d})	0.067* (0.038)	0.087** (0.039)
Indirect via beliefs ($\hat{a}\hat{e}$)	0.010 (0.009)	0.006 (0.005)
Indirect via attitudes ($\hat{c}\hat{f}$)	0.083** (0.034)	0.056* (0.033)
Indirect via beliefs→attitudes ($\hat{a}\hat{b}\hat{f}$)	0.021 (0.018)	0.031 (0.023)
Total	0.181*** (0.057)	0.181*** (0.057)
<i>Medical Chatbot</i>		
Direct (\hat{d})	0.001 (0.036)	-0.026 (0.037)
Indirect via beliefs ($\hat{a}\hat{e}$)	0.011* (0.007)	0.007* (0.005)
Indirect via attitudes ($\hat{c}\hat{f}$)	0.025 (0.034)	0.051 (0.035)
Indirect via beliefs→attitudes ($\hat{a}\hat{b}\hat{f}$)	0.031* (0.019)	0.037* (0.022)

WTD1 decomposition by system (continued)

Component	Sum indices	PCA indices
Total	0.068 (0.056)	0.068 (0.056)
Online Advertising		
Direct (\hat{d})	-0.009 (0.040)	-0.025 (0.041)
Indirect via beliefs ($\hat{a}\hat{e}$)	0.029*** (0.010)	0.004 (0.004)
Indirect via attitudes ($\hat{c}\hat{f}$)	0.097** (0.047)	0.117*** (0.046)
Indirect via beliefs→attitudes ($\hat{a}\hat{b}\hat{f}$)	0.041*** (0.014)	0.062** (0.022)
Total	0.158** (0.067)	0.158** (0.067)
Predictive Policing		
Direct (\hat{d})	0.078* (0.042)	0.124*** (0.044)
Indirect via beliefs ($\hat{a}\hat{e}$)	0.007 (0.007)	0.005 (0.004)
Indirect via attitudes ($\hat{c}\hat{f}$)	0.165*** (0.049)	0.111** (0.044)
Indirect via beliefs→attitudes ($\hat{a}\hat{b}\hat{f}$)	0.021 (0.021)	0.030 (0.024)
Total	0.270*** (0.069)	0.270*** (0.069)
Recommendation		
Direct (\hat{d})	0.001 (0.035)	0.020 (0.036)
Indirect via beliefs ($\hat{a}\hat{e}$)	0.050*** (0.012)	0.030*** (0.009)
Indirect via attitudes ($\hat{c}\hat{f}$)	0.003 (0.035)	-0.015 (0.035)
Indirect via beliefs→attitudes ($\hat{a}\hat{b}\hat{f}$)	0.059*** (0.014)	0.078*** (0.018)
Total	0.113** (0.053)	0.113** (0.053)
Robo-Advisors		
Direct (\hat{d})	0.032 (0.045)	0.025 (0.044)
Indirect via beliefs ($\hat{a}\hat{e}$)	-0.003 (0.009)	-0.002 (0.008)
Indirect via attitudes ($\hat{c}\hat{f}$)	0.007 (0.052)	0.012 (0.044)
Indirect via beliefs→attitudes ($\hat{a}\hat{b}\hat{f}$)	-0.008 (0.027)	-0.007 (0.028)
Total	0.028 (0.070)	0.028 (0.070)
Search Engine		
Direct (\hat{d})	-0.010 (0.039)	0.022 (0.040)
Indirect via beliefs ($\hat{a}\hat{e}$)	-0.005 (0.013)	-0.003 (0.009)
Indirect via attitudes ($\hat{c}\hat{f}$)	0.056* (0.032)	0.026 (0.032)
Indirect via beliefs→attitudes ($\hat{a}\hat{b}\hat{f}$)	-0.004 (0.011)	-0.007 (0.017)
Total	0.038 (0.055)	0.038 (0.055)
Social Media		
Direct (\hat{d})	-0.049 (0.047)	-0.070 (0.049)
Indirect via beliefs ($\hat{a}\hat{e}$)	0.005 (0.013)	0.004 (0.006)
Indirect via attitudes ($\hat{c}\hat{f}$)	0.065 (0.048)	0.080* (0.049)
Indirect via beliefs→attitudes ($\hat{a}\hat{b}\hat{f}$)	0.004 (0.011)	0.011 (0.018)

WTD1 decomposition by system (continued)

Component	Sum indices	PCA indices
Total	0.025 (0.070)	0.025 (0.070)

Note: Entries report respondent-level cluster bootstrap means with bootstrap standard errors in parentheses (500 replications). Stars based on bootstrap two-sided p -values (* $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$).

Table 23: WTD2 decomposition by system: Sum indices vs PCA indices

Component	Sum indices	PCA indices
<i>Algorithmic Trading</i>		
Direct (\hat{d})	-0.042 (0.035)	-0.036 (0.038)
Indirect via beliefs ($\hat{a}\hat{e}$)	0.024*** (0.009)	0.021*** (0.008)
Indirect via attitudes ($\hat{c}\hat{f}$)	0.057* (0.030)	0.049* (0.027)
Indirect via beliefs→attitudes ($\hat{a}\hat{b}\hat{f}$)	0.050*** (0.017)	0.055*** (0.018)
Total	0.089* (0.052)	0.089* (0.052)
<i>Credit Scoring</i>		
Direct (\hat{d})	-0.009 (0.038)	0.024 (0.041)
Indirect via beliefs ($\hat{a}\hat{e}$)	0.011 (0.008)	0.007 (0.006)
Indirect via attitudes ($\hat{c}\hat{f}$)	0.061 (0.036)	0.031 (0.032)
Indirect via beliefs→attitudes ($\hat{a}\hat{b}\hat{f}$)	0.023 (0.017)	0.024 (0.019)
Total	0.086 (0.054)	0.086 (0.054)
<i>Healthcare Diagnosis</i>		
Direct (\hat{d})	-0.037 (0.065)	0.017 (0.062)
Indirect via beliefs ($\hat{a}\hat{e}$)	0.023 (0.014)	0.017* (0.009)
Indirect via attitudes ($\hat{c}\hat{f}$)	0.138*** (0.038)	0.076** (0.034)
Indirect via beliefs→attitudes ($\hat{a}\hat{b}\hat{f}$)	0.035 (0.021)	0.050* (0.025)
Total	0.159* (0.082)	0.159* (0.082)
<i>Insurance Premium</i>		
Direct (\hat{d})	-0.009 (0.049)	-0.050 (0.052)
Indirect via beliefs ($\hat{a}\hat{e}$)	0.013 (0.009)	0.007 (0.006)
Indirect via attitudes ($\hat{c}\hat{f}$)	0.024 (0.038)	0.068* (0.036)
Indirect via beliefs→attitudes ($\hat{a}\hat{b}\hat{f}$)	0.027 (0.019)	0.030 (0.023)
Total	0.054 (0.069)	0.054 (0.069)
<i>Job Application</i>		
Direct (\hat{d})	0.024 (0.040)	0.047 (0.041)
Indirect via beliefs ($\hat{a}\hat{e}$)	0.010 (0.009)	0.009 (0.007)
Indirect via attitudes ($\hat{c}\hat{f}$)	0.076** (0.031)	0.047* (0.028)

WTD2 decomposition by system (continued)

Component	Sum indices	PCA indices
Indirect via beliefs→attitudes ($\hat{a}\hat{b}\hat{f}$)	0.019 (0.017)	0.026 (0.019)
Total	0.130** (0.057)	0.130** (0.057)
Medical Chatbot		
Direct (\hat{d})	0.006 (0.041)	-0.012 (0.042)
Indirect via beliefs ($\hat{a}\hat{e}$)	0.017* (0.010)	0.013* (0.008)
Indirect via attitudes ($\hat{c}\hat{f}$)	0.022 (0.030)	0.041 (0.028)
Indirect via beliefs→attitudes ($\hat{a}\hat{b}\hat{f}$)	0.027* (0.016)	0.030* (0.018)
Total	0.072 (0.056)	0.072 (0.056)
Online Advertising		
Direct (\hat{d})	0.042 (0.043)	0.025 (0.043)
Indirect via beliefs ($\hat{a}\hat{e}$)	0.002 (0.004)	-0.019** (0.008)
Indirect via attitudes ($\hat{c}\hat{f}$)	0.093** (0.045)	0.111*** (0.044)
Indirect via beliefs→attitudes ($\hat{a}\hat{b}\hat{f}$)	0.039*** (0.013)	0.059** (0.021)
Total	0.177*** (0.059)	0.177*** (0.059)
Predictive Policing		
Direct (\hat{d})	-0.061 (0.044)	-0.012 (0.050)
Indirect via beliefs ($\hat{a}\hat{e}$)	0.010 (0.011)	0.012 (0.010)
Indirect via attitudes ($\hat{c}\hat{f}$)	0.144*** (0.043)	0.089** (0.036)
Indirect via beliefs→attitudes ($\hat{a}\hat{b}\hat{f}$)	0.018 (0.018)	0.024 (0.019)
Total	0.112 (0.067)	0.112 (0.067)
Recommendation		
Direct (\hat{d})	-0.046 (0.042)	-0.028 (0.043)
Indirect via beliefs ($\hat{a}\hat{e}$)	-0.005 (0.005)	-0.025*** (0.008)
Indirect via attitudes ($\hat{c}\hat{f}$)	0.003 (0.037)	-0.016 (0.037)
Indirect via beliefs→attitudes ($\hat{a}\hat{b}\hat{f}$)	0.062*** (0.014)	0.083*** (0.019)
Total	0.014 (0.058)	0.014 (0.058)
Robo-Advisors		
Direct (\hat{d})	-0.016 (0.049)	-0.022 (0.055)
Indirect via beliefs ($\hat{a}\hat{e}$)	-0.004 (0.013)	-0.003 (0.012)
Indirect via attitudes ($\hat{c}\hat{f}$)	0.006 (0.043)	0.009 (0.034)
Indirect via beliefs→attitudes ($\hat{a}\hat{b}\hat{f}$)	-0.007 (0.022)	-0.005 (0.022)
Total	-0.021 (0.074)	-0.021 (0.074)
Search Engine		
Direct (\hat{d})	-0.036 (0.045)	-0.000 (0.048)
Indirect via beliefs ($\hat{a}\hat{e}$)	0.002 (0.004)	0.004 (0.009)
Indirect via attitudes ($\hat{c}\hat{f}$)	0.065* (0.037)	0.030 (0.037)

WTD2 decomposition by system (continued)

Component	Sum indices	PCA indices
Indirect via beliefs→attitudes ($\hat{a}\hat{b}\hat{f}$)	-0.005 (0.013)	-0.008 (0.019)
Total	0.026 (0.061)	0.026 (0.061)
<i>Social Media</i>		
Direct (\hat{d})	-0.004 (0.047)	-0.022 (0.049)
Indirect via beliefs ($\hat{a}\hat{e}$)	-0.000 (0.001)	-0.004 (0.008)
Indirect via attitudes ($\hat{e}\hat{f}$)	0.068 (0.050)	0.084* (0.051)
Indirect via beliefs→attitudes ($\hat{a}\hat{b}\hat{f}$)	0.004 (0.011)	0.011 (0.019)
Total	0.068 (0.072)	0.068 (0.072)

Note: Entries report respondent-level cluster bootstrap means with bootstrap standard errors in parentheses (500 replications).

Stars based on bootstrap two-sided p -values (* $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$).